

**“INTRATHECAL ROPIVACAINE VS BUPIVACAINE IN
ENDOSCOPIC UROLOGICAL SURGERIES”**

Submitted by

DR. ABHISHEK RAO KORDCAL

Dissertation submitted to the

**B. L. D. E. U'S SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE AND RESEARCH
CENTER, BIJAPUR
KARNATAKA**

In partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of

MD

In

ANAESTHESIOLOGY

Under the guidance of

**DR. VIJAYKUMAR TK M.D.
PROFESSOR
DEPARTMENT OF ANAESTHESIOLOGY**

**B. L. D. E. U'S
SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL &
RESEARCH CENTRE, BIJAPUR.**

2014

**B.L.D.E. UNIVERSITY
SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL
& RESEARCH CENTER, BIJAPUR
KARNATAKA.**

DECLARATION BY THE CANDIDATE

I hereby declare that this dissertation entitled “**INTRATHECAL ROPIVACAINE VS BUPIVACAINE IN ENDOSCOPIC UROLOGICAL SURGERIES**” is a bonafide and genuine research work carried out by me under the guidance of **DR. VIJAYKUMAR T KALLYANAPPAGOL** M.D. Professor, Department of Anaesthesiology.

Date:

Place: Bijapur

DR. ABHISHEK RAO KORDCAL

CERTIFICATE BY THE GUIDE

B. L. D. E. U.'S

**SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL &
RESEARCH CENTRE, BIJAPUR.**

This is to certify that the dissertation entitled “**INTRATHECAL ROPIVAINE VS BUPIVACAINE IN ENDOSCOPIC UROLOGICAL SURGERIES**” is a bonafide research work done by **DR. ABHISHEK RAO KORDCAL** in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the degree of MD in Anaesthesiology.

Date:

DR. VIJAYKUMAR T K M.D.

Place: Bijapur

**PROFESSOR
Department Of Anaesthesiology**

ENDORSEMENT BY THE HEAD OF DEPARTMENT

B. L. D. E. U.'S

**SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL &
RESEARCH CENTRE, BIJAPUR.**

This is to certify that the dissertation entitled “**INTRATHECAL ROPIVACAINE VS BUPIVACAINE IN ENDOSCOPIC UROLOGICAL SURGERIES**” is a bonafide research work done by **DR. ABHISHEK RAO KORDCAL** under the guidance of **DR. VIJAYKUMAR TK** M.D. Professor, Department of Anaesthesiology.

Date:

DR. D. G. TALIKOTI MD

Place: **Bijapur**

PROFESSOR & HEAD
DEPARTMENT OF ANAESTHESIOLOGY
B. L. D. E. U.'S SHRI. B. M. PATIL
MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL &
RESEARCH CENTRE, BIJAPUR.

ENDORSEMENT BY THE PRINCIPAL

B. L. D. E. U.'S

**SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL &
RESEARCH CENTRE, BIJAPUR.**

This is to certify that the dissertation entitled “**INTRATHECAL ROPIVACAINE VS BUPIVACAINE IN ENDOSCOPIC UROLOGICAL SURGERIES**” is a bonafide research work done by **DR. ABHISHEK RAO KORDCAL** under the guidance of **DR. VIJAYKUMAR TK** M.D. Professor, Department of Anaesthesiology.

Date:

Dr. M. S. BIRADAR MD

Place: **Bijapur**

PRINCIPAL
B. L. D. E. U'S Shri. B. M. Patil
Medical College Hospital &
Research Centre, Bijapur.

COPYRIGHT

Declaration by the candidate

I hereby declare that the **B. L. D. E. U.'S SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE & RESEARCH CENTER, BIJAPUR. KARNATAKA** shall have the rights to preserve, use and disseminate this dissertation / thesis in print or electronic format for academic / research purpose.

Date:

Place: Bijapur

DR. ABHISHEK RAO KORDCAL

© B.L.D.E. University of Health Sciences & Research Centre, Karnataka.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

On completion of this contribution of scientific document it gives me deep pleasure to acknowledge the guidance provided by my distinguished mentors.

With privilege and respect I like to express my gratitude and indebtedness to my Guide **DR. VIJAYKUMAR TK.**_{MD} Professor, Department of Anaesthesiology, Shri. B. M. Patil Medical College, Bijapur, for her constant inspiration, extensive encouragement and support, which she rendered in pursuit of my post-graduate studies and in preparing this dissertation.

I am forever grateful to **Dr. D. G. Talikoti** Prof. & Head of Department, **Dr. Vijaykumar** Prof., **Dr. R. R. Kusugal** Assoc Prof., **Dr. Vijay Katti** Assoc Prof., **Dr. Sridevi** Asst. Prof., **Dr. Renuka** Asst. Prof., **Dr. Narendra** Asst. Prof., **Dr. Mala Sajjanar**, **Dr. Lalitha**, **Dr. Ramesh**, **Dr. Prathiba**, **Dr. Santosh**, **Dr. Shivanand**, **Dr Prashanth**, **Dr Lahande**, **Dr Basavraj**, **Dr Mahendra** for there valuable help and guidance during my study.

I am extremely thankful to **Dr. M. S. Biradar**, Principal of B.L.D.E.U.'S Shri B. M.Patil Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Bijapur, for permitting me to utilize resources in completion of my work.

I am deeply indebted to my parents, whose constant encouragement and inspiration led me to successful completion of my dissertation work.

I thank **Mrs. Vijaya**, the statistician for her invaluable help in dealing all the statistical work in this study.

I am also thankful to my colleagues **Dr. Manasa**, **Dr. Harsha**, **Dr. Shivkumar**, **Dr. Prashanthini**, **Dr. Meera** and all my junior colleagues for their suggestions and advice.

My thanks to one and all in the **library Staff, Anaesthesia Staff, OT Staff** and all hospital Staff for their co-operation in my study.

Last but not the least; I convey my heartfelt gratitude to all the patients, without whose co-operation, this study would be incomplete.

My special thanks **Mr. Babu Patil Om Sai Internet**, Bijapur for computerizing my dissertation work in a right format. I sincerely appreciate his skills and recommended him for my junior colleagues.

Date:

Place: Bijapur

DR. ABHISHEK RAO KORDCAL

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

1. BMI	- Body mass index
2. CNS	- Central nervous system
3. CSF	- Cerebrospinal fluid
4. C_{max}	- Concentration maximum
5. Conc	- Concentration
6. ASA	- American Society of Anaesthesiologists
7. DBP	- Diastolic blood pressure
8. EC	- Effective concentration
9. ED	- Effective dose
10. g	- Gram
11. HR	- Heart rate
12. iv	- Intravenous
13. Kg	- Kilogram
14. L	- liters
15. LSCS	- Lower segment ceserean section
16. m	- Meter
17. MAP	- Mean arterial pressure
18. mcg	- Microgram
19. mg	- Milligram
20. min	- Minute
21. mL	- Milliliter
22. mol	- Mole
23. mmol	- Millimole
24. PDPH	- Postdural puncture headache
25. SBP	- Systolic blood pressure
26. sec	- Second
27. TURP	- Transurethral resection of prostate
28. V_{dss}	- Volume of distribution in steady state
29. yr	- Year
30. URS	- Ureteroscopic Lithotripsy

ABSTRACT

Study Objective: To compare the clinical effects of 2mL of 0.75% intrathecal isobaric ropivacaine with 3mL of 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine for endoscopic urological surgeries (TURP and URS)

Design: A prospective randomized controlled double blind study

Interventions: 142 patients belonging to ASA physical status 1, 2 & 3 scheduled for elective TURP and URS were randomly selected for the study and are divided into two groups of 71 each.

Group 1 Patients received 3mL of 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine intrathecally.

Group 2 Patients received 2mL of 0.75% isobaric ropivacaine intrathecally.

Onset of sensory block, onset and duration of motor block, highest level of sensory block, quality of anaesthesia and muscle relaxation, haemodynamic parameters and adverse effects if any were studied.

Results:

There was no significant difference between the two groups in mean time to onset of sensory block at T10, 5.79 ± 1.38 min with ropivacaine and 5.68 ± 1.57 min with bupivacaine. Highest level of sensory block attained was T6 in both groups. Time to two dermatomal regression was 129.54 ± 15.68 min in group 1 and 111.31 ± 22.69 min in group 2 which is highly significant statistically with a P- value of <0.001 .

Mean time required for sensory level to below T10 was similar between both groups.

Mean time of onset of motor block to Bromage score 1 was 4.59 ± 1.25 min in group 1 and 6.30 ± 1.44 min in group 2 ($p < 0.001$). Duration of motor block was 198.27 ± 18.60 min in group 1 and 133.74 ± 17.64 min in group 2. Mean duration of complete motor block in group 1 was 169.29 ± 17.60 min while that of group 2 was 108.98 ± 9.58 min which was clinically and statistically significant. Haemodynamic parameters were comparable in both groups except intraoperative hypotension requiring treatment was 41.7% of patients in group 1 and 18.60% of patients in group 2. Side effects were comparable in both groups.

Conclusion:

Ropivacaine 15 mg (2 mL of 0.75% isobaric) provides comparable quality of sensory block but has slower onset and significantly shorter duration of motor block compared to 15 mg (3mL of 0.5%) bupivacaine.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Sl. No.	PARTICULARS	Page No
1	INTRODUCTION	1-3
2	OBJECTIVES OF STUDY	4
3	REVIEW OF LITERATURE	5-8
4	ANATOMY & PHARMACOLOGY	9-34
5	MATERIALS AND METHODS	35-39
6	OBSERVATION AND RESULTS	40-60
7	DISCUSSION	61-66
8	CONCLUSION	67
9	SUMMARY	68-69
10	BIBLIOGRAPHY	70-74
11	ANNEXURES	75-81
	I.CASE PROFORMA II.CONSENT FORM III. KEY TO MASTER CHART IV. MASTER CHART V. ETHICAL CLEARANCE	

LIST OF TABLES

Sl No	Particulars	Page No.
1	Physiochemical properties of ropivacaine	24
2	Dosage recommendation for ropivacaine	30
3	Physiochemical properties of bupivacaine	32
4	Onset and duration of analgesia for bupivacaine	33
5	Pharmacokinetic property of bupivacaine	34
6	Modified Bromage scale	37
7	Comparison of Age, height and wieght	41
8	Percentage distribution of patients according to ASA grade	42
9	Surgery duration	43
10	Mean sensory block at T10	44
11	Highest sensory block	45
12	Two dermatomal regression time	46
13	Time required for sensory level to regress below T 10	46
14	Onset and duration of motor block(bromage scale)	48
15	Mean duration of motor block	49
16	Mean duration of complete motor block	49
17	Heart rate	52
18	Systolic blood pressure	54

19	Diastolic blood pressure	56
20	Comparison of mean blood pressure	58
21	Frequency of mephentaramine injection (Hypotension)	60

LIST OF FIGURES

Sl.No.	Figures	Page No
1	CURVE OF SPINE	9
2	TYPICAL VERTEBRA	10
3	LONGITUDINAL SECTION OF VERTEBRA	11
4	STRUCTURE OF ROPIVACAINE	24
5	STRUCTURE OF BUPIVACAINE	31
6	MATERIALS USED	36

LIST OF GRAPHS

SL No	GRAPHS	Page no.
1	COMPARISON OF AGE HEIGHT AND WEIGHT	41
2	PERCENTAGE DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO ASA GRADE	42
3	PERCENTAGE DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENT ACCORDING TO SURGERY DURATION	43
4	MEAN SENSORY BLOCK AT T10	44
5	HIEGHEST LEVEL OF SENSORY BLOCK	45
6	TIME REQUIRED FOR REGRESSION OF SENSORY BLOCK BELOW T10	47
7	ONSET AND DURATION OF MOTOR BLOCK (BROMAGE SCALE)	48
8	COMPARISON OF DURATION OF COMPLETE MOTOR BLOCK	50
9	COMPARISON OF HEART RATE	53
10	COMPARISON OF SYSTOLIC BLOOD PRESSURE	55
11	COMPARISON OF DIASTOLIC BLOOD PRESSURE	57
12	COMPARISON OF MEAN BLOOD PRESSURE	59
13	FREQUENCY OF INJ MEPHENTARAMINE ADMINISTRATION (HYPOTENSION)	60

INTRODUCTION

August Bier performed the first spinal anaesthesia more than a century ago by injecting cocaine into CSF of patient.

Quincke in 1891 demonstrated a safe, predictable means of performing lumbar puncture. In 1899, August Bier used Quincke's technique to inject cocaine in order to produce operative anaesthesia in six patients, the first real spinal anaesthesia. The first phase in the history of spinal anaesthesia from 1899 to 1905, was characterized by the use of only cocaine for spinal anaesthesia.¹

Bupivacaine, a pipercoloxylidide derivative synthesized in 1957 by Ekenstam and introduced in clinical practice in 1963 is widely used. It is a racemic mixture of D and L isomers. The dextro isomer makes bupivacaine more cardiotoxic drug. In 1979 Albright published an alarming editorial which associated bupivacaine with cardiac arrest during regional anaesthesia.

Bupivacaine depresses the rapid phase of depolarisation (V_{max}) in purkinje fibres and ventricle muscle². The rate of recovery from a use dependent block is slower in bupivacaine treated papillary muscle. This slow rate of recovery results in an incomplete restoration of sodium channel availability between action potentials. These effects explain the arrhythmogenic potential of bupivacaine⁴.

An important aspect of this toxicity is that it involves a significant degree of stereo specificity with S-isomer showing significantly less cardiac depression effect than R-isomer⁵.

In an editorial published in 1979, George A. Albright stated that bupivacaine might result in almost simultaneous seizure and cardiovascular collapse without

antecedent hypoxia from clinical doses following inadvertent intravascular administration²

One of the specific features of bupivacaine is that clinical evidence of accumulation of the drug in plasma may not be appreciated until a fairly late stage because of its high affinity for plasma protein binding sites. The free concentration of the drug in plasma remains low until all the protein binding sites are fully occupied, after which it increases rapidly and toxicity can occur without patient exhibiting signs of CNS toxicity before cardiovascular collapse.^{6,7}

Bupivacaine has been shown to have selective cardiac effects related to the slow rate at which it dissociates from sodium channels.^{4,8} An important aspect of this toxicity is that it involves a significant degree of stereo specificity with 'S' isomer showing significantly less cardiotoxic effect.⁹ These findings generated the search for an alternative to bupivacaine concentrating on amide linked agents which in current practice have largely replaced the ester type drugs. With the advantage in stereo selective synthesis it was found that agents composed of single enantiomer have clinical advantage over racemic preparations.¹⁰

Ropivacaine is an amino amide local anaesthetic agent. It is monohydrate of the hydrochloride salt of 1-propyl 2, 6-pipecoloxylidide and is prepared as pure enantiomer form. This drug was first registered for clinical use in 1996.¹¹

The physiochemical property of ropivacaine suggests that its rate of onset (related to pain) is similar to that of bupivacaine, and that its absolute potency (lipid solubility) and duration of effects (protein binding) is slightly less compared to

bupivacaine. Ropivacaine has slightly rapid plasma clearance and shorter elimination $t_{1/2}$ than that of racemic bupivacaine.¹²

Ropivacaine administration by intravenous infusion was found to be less toxic than bupivacaine in human volunteers. Mild CNS symptoms and minor cardiovascular toxicity as measured by changes in contractility and conductivity occurred at lesser dosage and lower plasma concentration with bupivacaine compared to ropivacaine.¹³

When compared with same concentration of bupivacaine, ropivacaine produces identical sensory block.^{14,15,16,17} Motor block produced by ropivacaine was found to be slower in onset,¹⁵ less intense and shorter in duration.^{14,15} But some studies have shown similar motor effects with ropivacaine and bupivacaine.^{16,17} Because of sensory motor dissociation, ropivacaine should be a favourable local anaesthetic for day care surgery and could be associated with earlier postoperative mobilization than bupivacaine.¹⁸

The newer drug ropivacaine being comparatively less cardiotoxic, it also produces minimal motor block of shorter duration¹⁹ which relieves the psychological distress of being immobile for a long period of time²⁰

Hence, the purpose of the study is to assess the duration of sensory and motor blockade of ropivacaine and side effects if any compared to bupivacaine

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study compared the effects of 2mL (15mg) intrathecal isobaric ropivacaine (0.75%) with 3mL (15mg) of hyperbaric bupivacaine (0.5%).

We compared

- Onset and duration of sensory block
- Onset and duration of motor block
- Maximum height of sensory block
- Quality of anaesthesia
- Haemodynamic parameters
- Complications/side effects if any

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Susan B. McDonald²¹ conducted study on 18 healthy volunteers randomized into three equal groups to receive a spinal administration with bupivacaine and second with Ropivacaine of equal mg doses (11.8 or 12mg) of 0.25%drug with 5% dextrose. They concluded low dose hyperbaric spinal ropivacaine does not appear to offer an advantage over bupivacaine for use in outpatient anaesthesia.

Andrea Casati et al.²² compared unilateral spinal anaesthesia with hyperbaric bupivacaine, Ropivacaine or levobupivacaine for inguinal herniorrhaphy in 60 patients. they concluded that 8 mg of levobupivacaine or 12 mg of Ropivacaine are acceptable alternatives to 8 mg bupivacaine when limiting spinal block at the operative side for inguinal hernia repair.

Osama Al. Abdulhadiet et al.²³ compared hyperbaric spinal ropivacaine to hyperbaric spinal bupivacaine for LSCS in a prospective, randomized, double blind study of 66 patients. They concluded side effects did not differ between the two groups. The Ropivacaine patients expressed significant higher satisfaction level and faster regression of block.

D.A. McNamee et al.²⁴ compared plain Ropivacaine 5mg with bupivacaine 5mg for major orthopedic surgery in 66 patients and found that more rapid postoperative recovery and motor function was seen in ropivacaine compared with bupivacaine.

J.F Luck et al.²⁵ compared hyperbaric solution of racemic bupivacaine levobupicaine. Ropivacaine in 60 patients for elective surgery. They concluded hyperbaric Ropivacaine provides reliable spinal anaesthesia of shorter duration than

bupivacaine or levobupivacaine. The recovery profile of Ropivacaine may be helpful where prompt mobilization is required.

Helena Kallio et al.¹⁸ conducted prospective, randomized, double study in 90 patients undergoing elective day care minor lower extremity surgery under spinal anaesthesia and opined that the major advantage of Ropivacaine 15mg in particular, is a faster motor recovery compared with bupivacaine 10mg. the groups did not differ in haemodynamics.

Chang-Jong Chung et al.²⁶ evaluated the clinical efficacy and safety of spinal anaesthesia with 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine for caesarean delivery in sixty full term parturient. They concluded that Ropivacaine produced similar and clinically effective spinal anaesthesia with shorter duration of sensory and motor block compared to hyperbaric bupivacaine.

M.Mantouvaloy et al.²⁷ performed a study to compare the anaesthetic efficacy and safety of three local anaesthetic agents racemic bupivacaine its two isomers Ropivacaine and levobupivacaine for lower abdominal surgery. In their study Ropivacaine presented a slower onset and a shorter duration of motor block, as well as a faster resolution of sensory block compared with the two other local anaesthetics even though was not associated with a significant acceleration of home discharge.

Jean-more Matinovsky et al.²⁸ compared intrathecal Ropivacaine to bupivacaine in 100 patients scheduled for TURP. They concluded that 15 mg of intrathecal Ropivacaine provided similar motor and haemodynamic effects but less potent anaesthesia than 10mg of bupivacaine for endoscopic urological surgery.

P. Gautier et al.²⁹ conducted a study to detect if intrathecal Ropivacaine and levobupivacaine provides anaesthesia (satisfactory analgesia and muscular relaxation) and postoperative analgesia of similar quality to bupivacaine in patients undergoing caesarean section. Ninety parturient were enrolled to receive combined spinal epidural technique. Patients were divided into three groups and randomly assigned to receive one of the following isobaric intrathecal solutions: bupivacaine 8 mg, levobupivacaine 8 mg or Ropivacaine 12 mg all combined with sufentanil 2.5 mg conclusion was that racemic mixture bupivacaine 8 mg with sufentanil 2.5 mg remains an adequate choice for caesarean section under spinal anaesthesia. The success rate is significantly superior to levobupivacaine 8mg but not to ropivacaine 12 mg.

C.O. Ogun et al.³⁰ conducted a prospective, double blind, randomized study to evaluate the effects of intrathecal isobaric bupivacaine 0.5% plus morphine and isobaric Ropivacaine 0.5% plus morphine combinations in women undergoing caesarean deliveries. Twenty five parturient received Ropivacaine 15mg and morphine 150mg and twenty five parturient received bupivacaine 15mg and morphine 150mg and observed that time to reach complete motor block was shorter and time to complete recovery from motor block was longer in bupivacaine morphine group than Ropivacaine morphine group. Time to regression of two dermatomes and time for the block to recorded S2 dermatome were similar in both groups and constructed that intrathecal isobaric Ropivacaine 0.5% plus 150 mcg morphine provided sufficient anaesthesia for caesarean delivery. The ropivacaine morphine combination resulted in shorter motor block, similar sensory block and postoperative analgesia. hypotension and pruritus were the most common side effects in both groups during operation.

Neva Boztug et al.³⁸ compared the effects of intrathecal Ropivacaine with bupivacaine in a Dose of 2:1 for outpatient arthroscopic knee surgery by conducting randomized, single-blinded study. 90 patients scheduled for outpatient arthroscopic knee surgery received 3 ml solution of either 15 mg of isobaric Ropivacaine or 7.5 mg of isobaric bupivacaine and recorded the onset and offset times for sensory and motor block, highest level of sensory block, duration of sensory and motor block, first ambulation, urination, and discharge ambulation, urination, and discharge time, Mean arterial pressure, and heart rate were recorded. They concluded that isobaric Ropivacaine 15 mg provided a higher sensory block level and shorter sensory onset and offset times than did 7.5 mg of isobaric bupivacaine and 15 mg of Ropivacaine intrathecally is adequate for lower extremity surgery of short duration. Haemodynamic changes were similar between the groups.

ANATOMY

Proficiency in spinal anaesthesia requires thorough understanding of the anatomy of the spine and the spinal cord. The anaesthesiologist must not only be familiar with the surface anatomy of the spine but must also develop a mental picture of three dimensional anatomy of deeper structures.

The curve of the spine³²

FIGURE 1: CURVE OF THE SPINE

In adult, the spinal column has four curves.

1. Cervical curve: anterior convexity
2. Thoracic curve: posterior convexity
3. Lumbar curve: anterior convexity
4. Sacrococcygeal: posterior convexity

Vertebrae:

The spine consists of 33 vertebrae

Cervical -7

Thoracic-12

Lumbar-5

Sacrum-5(fused)

Coccyx-4(fused)

The typical vertebra:

FIGURE 2: TYPICAL VERTEBRA

It is composed of:

- The body anteriorly bears the weight.
- Two pedicles that project posteriorly from the body.
- Two laminae that connect pedicles.
- The laminae gives rise to transverse processes that project laterally and spinous process that projects posteriorly.
- The pedicles contains superior and inferior vertebral notch through which the spinal nerve exits the spinal canal.

- Superior and inferior articular processes arise at the junction of the lamina and pedicles and form joints with the adjoining vertebra.

Ligaments:

The vertebral bodies are stabilized by five ligaments

- 1. Anterior and posterior longitudinal ligaments:** They run along the anterior and posterior surfaces of the vertebral bodies.
- 2. Supraspinous ligament:** It is a strong thick fibrous band connecting the tips of spines from 7th cervical vertebrae to the sacrum. This may become ossified in old age and render penetration with a thin needle impossible.

FIGURE 3: LONGITUDINAL SECTION OF VERTEBRAE

- 3. Interspinous ligament:** It attaches between the spinous processes, blends posteriorly with supraspinous ligament and anteriorly with ligamentum flavum.

- 4. Ligamentum flavum:** Is a tough, wedge shaped ligament composed of elastin. It consists of right and left portions that span vertebral laminae and fuse in the midline to varying degree. Ligamentum flavum is thickest in the midline, measuring 3 to 5 mm at the L2- L3 interspace in adults.

Contents of vertebral canal:

- Spinal cords and meninges
- CSF
- Spinal nerve roots
- Vessels, fat, areolar tissue

Meninges:

The spinal meninges consists of three protective layers, which are continuous with cranial meninges

- Dura mater
- Arachnoid mater
- Pia mater

Dura mater:³³ It is the outer most and thickest meningeal tissue. This begins at the foramen magnum where it fuses with the periosteum of the skull. Caudally it ends approximately at S2 where it fuses with filum terminale. It extends laterally along spinal nerve roots and becomes continuous with the connective tissues of the epineurium at the level of inter vertebral foramina. The dura mater is composed of randomly arranged collagen fibers, and longitudinally and circumferentially arranged elastin fibers.

It is largely acellular except for a layer of cells that forms the border between the dura and arachnoid mater. Despite the lack of cellular elements, the inner edge of

the duramater is highly vascular, due to this it forms an important route for drug clearance from epidural and subarachnoid space.

Arachnoid mater: It is a delicate, avascular membrane composed of overlapping layers of flattened cells with connective fibers running between the cellular layers. These cells are interconnected by frequent tight junctions and occluding junctions. These connections account for the fact that arachnoid mater is the main barrier for drugs moving between the epidural space and spinal cord.

Arachnoid mater herniates through dura into epidural space near the spinal nerve roots forming arachnoid granulations, these granulations serve as exit for the drugs from subarachnoid space. The subarachnoid space lies between arachnoid mater and pia mater and contains CSF, this in continuity with cranial CSF provides route for drugs to reach brain.

Pia mater: It is adherent to spinal cord and composed of thin layer of connective tissue cells interposed with collagen. Trabeculae connect the pia mater with arachnoid mater and the cells of these two meninges blend together along the trabeculae, fenestrations in pia mater aids the communication of spinal cord with subarachnoid space.

Cerebrospinal fluid:³⁴

CSF is a complex solution containing electrolytes, proteins, glucose, neurotransmitters nucleotides, amino acids and other substances. It is produced by ultrafiltration of plasma in choroid plexus and cerebral/spinal capillaries and by oxidation of glucose.

CSF volume is 100 to 160mL in adults and it is produced at the rate of 20 to 25mL/hour and entire CSF volume is replaced roughly every 6hrs. It is removed by

arachnoid villi present in superior sagittal sinus and along spinal nerve roots. Cine-Magnetic resonance imaging and cine-computerised tomography showed that CSF oscillates in cephalocaudal axis with frequency with that of heart rate and net CSF movement is estimated at 0.04% per oscillation. Significance of this motion is that CSF cannot be relied on to distribute drugs in subarachnoid space. In single shot spinal anaesthesia kinetic energy of injection and baricity of the solution serve to distribute the drug.

Characteristics and Composition of CSF:

Specific gravity	1.003-1.009
Vol. in spinal subarchnoid space	20 mL
Pressure	110mm of water
Protein	200-400mg/L
Glucose	2.5-4.5mmol/L
Chloride	123-128mmol/L
Sodium	140-150mmol/L
Bicarbonate	25-30mmol/ L
pH	7.4-7.6

Spinal cord:

Medulla oblongata continues as spinal cord below level of foramen magnum and it tapers off into a conical extremity known as conus medullaris.

In first trimester, fetal spinal cord extends up to the end of sacrum. As vertebral column grows faster than spinal cord, at birth it ends at the level of third lumbar vertebra. In an adult the tip of spinal cord lies at the level of first lumbar

vertebra. However, in 30% of individuals the spinal cord may end at T12, while in 10% it may extend to L3.

Spinal Segment:

The spinal cord gives rise to 31 pairs of spinal nerves, each composed of anterior motor root and posterior sensory root. The portion of the spinal cord that gives rise to single spinal nerve is called a cord segment. The skin area innervated by a given spinal nerve and its corresponding cord segment is called a dermatome.

31 pairs of spinal nerves are as follows.

- a. Cervical 8
- b. Thoracic 12
- c. Lumbar 5
- d. Sacral 5
- e. Coccygeal 1

Spinal nerves:

Two roots, anterior root and posterior root fuse together forming a spinal nerve. Sympathetic preganglionic axons arise from cells in the intermediolateral horn of the spinal cord from T1 to L2. The posterior root is larger than anterior and the efferent impulses from the whole of the body including the viscera passes through these roots. Each posterior root has a ganglion and conveys fibers of pain, touch, temperature, deep sensation from bone, joints and muscle and tendons, efferent from the viscera (accompanying sympathetic) and vasodilator fibers.

Segmental levels:

Perineum	S1-S4
Inguinal region	L4
Umbilicus	T10
Subcostal	T6-9
Nipple line	T4-T5
Second intercostalspace	T2
Clavicle	C3-4

The skin above the nipple has double innervations from C3 and C4 and from T2, 3, 4. So even with a successful block to C8 there will be some sensation above the nipple line.

Blood supply of spinal cord:

The principle arterial supply to the spinal cord is derived from one anterior and two posterior arteries that descend from level of foramen magnum.

The anterior spinal artery is formed at the foramen magnum by union of a branch from each vertebral artery. It is the largest of the vessels and supplies a large anterior portion of the cord.

There are two posterior spinal arteries, one on each side. They are derived at the base of the brain either directly from the vertebral artery or more often from a primary branch of each vertebral artery. They supply the posterior one-third of the spinal cord. This supply is augmented by spinal branches of the vertebral, ascending cervical posterior, intercostals, lumbar and lateral sacral arteries, which pass through the intervertebral foramina. Venous drainage is through a plexus of anterior and

posterior veins in the neck, the azygous veins in the thorax, lumbar veins in the abdomen and lateral sacral veins in the pelvis.

When a needle is inserted into the subarachnoid space the following structures are traversed.

1. Skin
2. Subcutaneous tissue
3. Supraspinous ligament
4. Interspinous ligament
5. Ligamentum flavum
6. Areolar tissue or epidural space
7. Spinal dura matter

PHYSIOLOGY OF NEURAXIAL BLOCKADE

The physiological effects of neuraxial blocks are often misinterpreted as complication. Clear distinction should be made between the physiologic effects of an anaesthetic technique and complications, which imply some harm to the patient.

Cardiovascular effects:³³

- Decrease in heart rate
- Decrease in arterial blood pressure

These effects are due to sympathectomy that accompanies the technique and depends on height of the block, which is typically described as extending from two to six dermatomes above the sensory level with spinal anaesthesia.

This sympathectomy causes venous and arterial dilatation, but because of the large amount of the blood (75% of total blood volume) and limited amount of smooth muscles in the venous system venodilation effect predominates. In contrast smooth muscle tone on arterial side is retained to some extent. After neuraxial block if cardiac output is maintained, fall in peripheral vascular resistance is 15% to 18%, in elderly with cardiac disease vascular resistance may decrease by 25%.

Heart rate during high neuraxial blockade typically decreases as result of blockade of cardioaccelerator fibers rising from T1 to T4. The heart rate may also decrease because of a fall in right atrial filling, which decreases outflow from intrinsic chronotropic stretch receptors located in the right atrium and great veins.

Respiratory effects:

Alterations in pulmonary variables in healthy patients during neuraxial block are usually of little consequence. Tidal volume remains unchanged during high spinal anaesthesia and vital capacity decreases by a small amount (4.05 to 3.73L). This decrease in vital capacity is a result of a decrease in expiratory reserve volume related to paralysis of the abdominal muscles necessary for forced expiration rather than a decrease in phrenic or diaphragmatic function.

The rare respiratory arrest associated with spinal anaesthesia is also unrelated to phrenic or inspiratory dysfunction but rather to hypoperfusion of the respiratory centers in the brainstem. This concept is supported by the evidence of disappearance of apnea as soon as pharmacologic and fluid therapies have restored cardiac output and blood pressure. This would not be the case if phrenic paralysis induced by high level of local anaesthetic was the cause of apnea.

Neuraxial block should be used cautiously in respiratory cripples because of paralysis of respiratory muscles. Except for severely compromised patients with respiratory failure, inspiratory muscle function during neuraxial blocks should be adequate to maintain ventilator function.

Gastrointestinal function:

Nausea and vomiting may be associated with neuraxial block in up to 20% of patients and are primarily related to gastrointestinal hyper peristalsis caused by unopposed parasympathetic activity. This gastrointestinal hyper peristalsis has the advantage of providing excellent surgical conditions because of a contracted gut. The decrease in hepatic blood flow during spinal anaesthesia parallels the decrease in mean arterial pressure. When epidural analgesia is continued into postoperative period, there may be a protective effect on the gastric mucosa because intramucosal pH is higher during postoperative epidural analgesia than systemic analgesia.

Renal function:

Despite predictable decrease in renal blood flow accompanying neuraxial blockade, the decrease is of little physiologic importance. One aspect of genitourinary function that is of clinical importance is the belief that neuraxial blocks are a frequent cause of urinary retention, which delays discharge of outpatients and necessitates bladder catheterization in inpatients. Lower concentrations of local anaesthetics are necessary for paralysis of bladder function than for motor block in lower extremities.

In any case it is prudent to avoid administration of excessive volumes of crystalloid solutions under spinal anaesthesia and to individualize the requirement for voiding before discharge in low risk ambulatory surgery patients after short acting spinal anaesthetics.

Endocrine effects:

Spinal anaesthesia has been shown to inhibit many endocrine metabolic changes associated with stress response. The effect is greatest with lower abdomen and lower extremity procedures than upper abdominal and thoracic procedures. This effect is due to decrease in afferent sensory information that helps to initiate stress response.

Factors affecting the block height:

Following factors influence the block height

- | | |
|---|---------------------------|
| 1. Patient characteristics | 2. Technique of injection |
| Age | Site of injection |
| Weight | Direction of bevel |
| Gender | Rate of injection |
| Intra-abdominal pressure | |
| Anatomic configuration of spinal column | |
| 3. Characteristics of local anesthetic solution | |
| Baricity | |
| Dose of local anesthetic solution | |
| Concentration of local anesthetic solution | |
| Volume of local anesthetic solution | |

Baricity and patient position:

Baricity is defined as ratio of density of local anaesthetic solution divided by density of CSF. Solutions that have the same density as CSF have baricity of 1.0000 and are termed isobaric, solutions that are more dense than CSF are termed hyperbaric, whereas solutions that are less dense than CSF are termed hypobaric.

Baricity is important in determining local anaesthetic spread and block height, because gravity causes hyperbaric solutions to flow downward in CSF to most dependent regions in spinal column, whereas hypobaric solutions tends to rise in CSF. In contrast, gravity has no effect on distribution of truly isobaric solutions.

Dose, volume, and concentration:

These three are interdependent variables which affect block height and are difficult to conduct and interpret because it is not possible to change one variable without changing another. But some conclusions are drawn based on some studies with isobaric solutions that, when dose is held constant, injected volume and drug concentration will not affect block height. Drug dose appears to play a small role in determining block height.

Injection site:

Has important effect on block height. Sensory block height resulting from isobaric bupivacaine is reduced by two dermatomes per interspace.

Patient characteristics:

Neither patient height nor age correlates with clinical characteristics of block. However, CSF volume and weight were correlated with peak block height. BMI is significant predictor of time of onset of complete sensory block.

Controllable factors:

- Dose (volume x concentration)
- Site of injection along the neuraxis
- Baricity of local anaesthetic solution
- Posture of the patient

Factors not controllable:

- Volume of cerebrospinal fluid
- Density of cerebrospinal fluid

The fate of injected agents:

There is fall in the concentration soon after the injection of anaesthetic agent into the subarachnoid space. This is due to the following processes:

- Dilution and mixing in CSF
- Diffusion and distribution to neural tissues
- Uptake and fixation by neural tissues
- Vascular absorption and elimination

Through arachnoid villi

Directly from capillary bed of parenchyma

Initially, there is rapid reduction in concentration of drug, which occurs within 2-3 min soon after injection of drug. This is due to mixing and dilution with CSF. This depends on the force or rate of injection of drug and to the amount or volume of fluid in spinal subarachnoid space

The sequence of nerve modality block:

- Vasomotor block – dilation of skin vessels and increased cutaneous blood flow
- Temperature - cold first then warmth
- Loss of temperature discrimination
- Pain – pin prick
- Loss of tactile sensation

- Motor paralysis
- Pressure sense
- Proprioception and vibration

Sympathetic blockade is the major determinant of physiologic responses to subarachnoid anaesthesia. Indirect effects of spinal anaesthesia may be considered the result of paralysis of these nerves.

PHARMACOLOGY

Local anaesthetics are chemical compounds which are capable of reversibly inhibiting the propagation of impulses in nerve cells.

Classification:

Clinically useful agents can be classified into two groups depending on the link between the aromatic portion and the intermediate chain. The amino ester group has an ester link and includes procaine, chlorprocaine and amethocaine. The amino amides have an amide link between the aromatic head and the intermediate chain and include lignocaine, bupivacaine, mepivacaine, prilocaine, etidocaine and ropivacaine.

ROPIVACAINE:^{5, 11, 36}

Ropivacaine is a member of the amino amide class of local anaesthetics. The parent compound of ropivacaine, like bupivacaine and mepivacaine was, first synthesized in the 1950s, but bupivacaine and mepivacaine were selected for further development as short and long acting agents respectively. It was only when concerns about the cardiotoxicity of bupivacaine became apparent that ropivacaine was evaluated fully. It was registered for clinical use in 1996.

Ropivacaine is used as ropivacaine hydrochloride, which is chemically described as S-(-)-1-propyl-2, 6'-pipecoloxylidide hydrochloride monohydrate. It is structurally similar to bupivacaine. Butyl group of bupivacaine is replaced by a propyl group to form ropivacaine.

It is prepared and marketed as pure S-enantiomer. Ropivacaine has an enantiomer purity of 99.5%. It is the first enantiomerically pure local anaesthetic drug to be made available.

Ropivacaine has a chemical formula of $C_{17}H_{26}N_2O \cdot HCl \cdot H_2O$ and the following structural formula.

FIGURE 4: STRUCTURE OF ROPIVACAINE

TABLE 1: PHYSIOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF ROPIVACAINE

Molecular weight of chloride salt	328g/mol
Molecular weight of base	274g/mol
pKa	8.07
Partition co-efficient (N-heptane/buffer)	2.9
Mean uptake ratio (Rat Sciatic nerve)	1.8
Protein binding	94%

The lipid solubility of ropivacaine is intermediate to lidocaine and bupivacaine. Plasma protein binding is marginally less than bupivacaine but pKa is identical to that of bupivacaine.

Presentation:

Clear colourless preservative free solution containing 2.0, 5.0, 7.5 and 10 mg/mL concentration. The specific gravity ranges from 1.002 – 1.005 at 25°C.

Clinical Pharmacology:

Mode of action:

Ropivacaine, like other amide local anaesthetics acts by blocking the generation and the conductance of nerve impulses by increasing the threshold for electrical excitation in the nerve, by slowing the propagation of the nerve impulse, and by reducing the rise of action potential.

Pharmacodynamics:

Neuropharmacology:

Ropivacaine in common with other local anaesthetics reversibly blocks the conduction of nerve impulses by decreasing the permeability of nerve cell membranes to sodium ions.

Clinically the order of loss of nerve function is as follows:

1. Pain
2. Temperature
3. Touch
4. Proprioception
5. Skeletal muscle tone

As ropivacaine has a high pKa and low lipid solubility, it preferentially blocks C fibers which gives it the property of differential blockade making it a desirable drug for labor analgesia and postoperative needs.

Peripheral vascular effects:

Median epidural blood flow decreased from 5mL/min/100gm of tissue at baseline to 3mL/min/100gm of tissue. 30 minutes after a loading dose of 100mg followed by a continuous infusion ropivacaine 5mg/mL at a rate of 40mg/hour. In larger volumes or high concentration, ropivacaine does not have a vasoconstrictive effect. In human tissue it was found that vasoconstriction induced by low concentrations of ropivacaine (upto 1.5mmol) was reversed at higher concentrations.

Cardiovascular effects:

At high doses in animal studies (in vitro) it significantly reduced mean arterial pressure (by 11%), ventricular dp/dt by 32%, and increased the left ventricular end diastolic pressure (LVEDP) by 32%. Ropivacaine significantly increased great cardiac venous blood flow. When used in epidural neuraxial blockade, the cardiovascular effect of ropivacaine is similar to that of bupivacaine. Both drugs significantly decreased mean arterial blood pressure and significantly increased heart rate, stroke volume, and cardiac output and ejection fraction.

Cardiac electro-physiological effects:

The cardiovascular toxicity of local anaesthetic is complex involving direct effects on the myocardium, on vascular tissue (both smooth muscle and its neuronal supply) and on the central innervation of the heart. In both neuronal and cardiac Na⁺ channels, the S-isomers of piperidine containing local anaesthetics are less potent than R-isomers.

More important to the direct cardiotoxic actions is the very slow reversal of Na⁺ channel blockade, a hallmark of bupivacaine which is considerably faster with ropivacaine. Such slow drug reversal has been related to persistent conduction slowing re-entry circuits and the development of ventricular tachycardia leading to fibrillation. In addition to these electrical differences, the negative inotropic potency of ropivacaine on isolated cardiac tissue appears to be considerably less than that of bupivacaine. Both electrical and mechanical differences may arise from the selective inhibition of Ca²⁺ current by bupivacaine.

Blocking of potassium channels may contribute to the cardiotoxic effects of local anaesthetic drugs by promoting a lengthening of cardiac action potential. Ropivacaine has been shown to block open human potassium channels in a concentration dependent manner in vitro.

The cardio-depressive effects of ropivacaine has been shown to be dependent on the extra-cellular potassium concentration compared with low concentrations (2.7mmol/L, a sub-physiological level) high potassium concentrations (8.7mmol/L, a supra-physiological level) reduced the EC₅₀ of ropivacaine with respect to negative inotropic effect and maximum upstroke velocity. Ropivacaine depresses cardiac conductivity and conductance less than bupivacaine. It has less effect on cardiac rhythm also. Ropivacaine 5.33mg and bupivacaine 4mg respectively increased QRS interval by 75% and 155% and QT by 18% and 20%.

CNS effects:

Ropivacaine can produce both stimulation and depression of central nervous system. Stimulation is manifested as restlessness, tremors and shivering progressing

to convulsions followed by depression and coma progressing to respiratory arrest. It has a primary depressant effect on the medulla and higher centers.

Pharmacokinetic properties:

The systemic concentration of ropivacaine is dependent on the total dose and concentration of drug administered the route of administration, the patient's haemodynamic/circulatory condition and the vascularity of administration site.

Absorption and Distribution:

After intravenous administration:

Ropivacaine 50mg infused intravenously over a 15 minute period produced peak plasma concentration (C_{max}) ranging between 1.1 and 2.0mg/L (Mean 1.5mg/L) The mean volume of distribution in steady state (V_{dss}) is 41 litres with a standard deviation of 7 litres. However, ropivacaine is extensively bound to plasma proteins (94%) mostly to alpha 1 -acid glycoprotein and V_{dss} increased to 742 litres when calculated according to concentration of free drug in plasma.

After epidural administration:

From the epidural space ropivacaine shows complete and biphasic absorption. The half-life of two phases (mean + SD) are 14+ 7 minutes and 14+ 7 hours respectively. The slow absorption is the rate- limiting factor in the elimination of ropivacaine which explains why the terminal half-life is longer after epidural than after intravenous administration.

Metabolism:

Ropivacaine is extensively metabolized in the liver predominantly by aromatic hydroxylation mediated by microsomal cytochrome P4501A to 2', 6'-

Pipecoloxylidide-3' hydroxyl ropivacaine and 4'-hydroxy ropivacaine. The extent of dealkylation and 3-hydroxylation of ropivacaine correlates well with the level of CYP3 & CYP4A4 isoenzymes in hepatic microsomes respectively. Low concentration of conjugates is found in plasma.

Elimination:

The kidney is the main excretory organ of the metabolites. Approximately 37% of the total dose is excreted in the urine as both free and conjugated forms. 86% of ropivacaine is excreted in urine after intravenous administration of which only 1% is unchanged. The main plasma clearance is 387 ± 107 L/min and unbound plasma clearance is 7.2 ± 16 L/min. Renal clearance is 1.1 mL/min. The terminal half-life is 1.8 ± 0.7 hour after I.V administration and 4.2 ± 1 hour after epidural administration.

Complications:

Adverse effects are reported in studies after use of ropivacaine.

Incidence >5%:

Hypotension, nausea, vomiting, back pain.

Incidence 1 to 5%:

Fever, headache, urinary retention, dizziness, rigor, hypertension, tachycardia, anxiety, fetal distress, neonatal disorders including jaundice, tachypnea, respiratory distress, vomiting.

Incidence <1%:

- Application site reactions.
- Vasovagal reaction, syncope, nonspecific ECG abnormalities, extrasystole, atrial fibrillation.
- Poor progression of labor, uterine atony

- Foecal incontinence, tenesmus.
- Tinnitus
- Myalgia, cramps
- Tremor, Horner's syndrome, dyskinesia, neuropathy, vertigo, agitation, confusion, hallucination.
- Dyspnea, bronchospasm.

Dosage recommendation for ropivacaine

TABLE 2: DOSAGE RECOMMENDATIONS FOR ROPIVACAINE

	Conc (%)	Volume (ml)	Dose (mg)	Onset (Min)	Duration (Hours)
Lumbar epidural administration surgery	0.5%	15-30	75-150	15-30	2-4
	0.75%	15-25	113-118	10-20	3-5
	1%		150-200	10-20	4-6
Lumbar epidural administration caesarean section	0.5%	20-30	100-150	15-25	2-4
Thoracic epidural administration	0.5%	5-15	25-75	10-20	n/a
Major nerve block(eg brachial plexus block)	0.5%	35-50	175-250	15-30	5-8
Field block(eg minor nerve blocks and infiltration)	0.5%	35-50	175-250	15-30	5-8

BUPIVACAINE: 4, 5, 11, 36

It is a synthetic local anaesthetic, which belongs to the amide group. It is an anilide compound, which was first prepared by A. F. Ekenstam in 1957 and was marketed as Marcaine.

Bupivacaine is the chloride salt of 1-N-Butyl-DL-piperidine-2-Carboxylic-2,6-dimethyl anilide. It differs from mepivacaine only by the presence of a butyl group, which is substituted for methyl group on the piperidine nitrogen.

Chemical formula- $C_{18}H_{28}N_2O$ HCL

Chemical Structure- It is marketed as a racemic mixture of dextro and levo isomers.

Structural Formula:

FIGURE 5 :STRUCTURE OF BUIPIVACAINE

Physiochemical Properties of bupivacaine

The base of bupivacaine is sparingly soluble but the hydrochloride salt is readily soluble in water.

TABLE 3: PHYSIOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF BUPIVACAINE

Molecular weight of chloride salt	325g/mol
Molecular weight of base	288g/mol
pKa	8.1
Partition of co-efficient(N heptanes/buffer)	10
Mean uptake ratio(rat sciatic nerve)	3.3
Protein binding	95%

Presentation:

1. As a clear, colorless solution containing 0.25/0.5/0.75 % bupivacaine hydrochloride
2. 0.25/0.5% solutions are available combined with 1:200000 adrenaline.
3. A 0.5% (Heavy) solution containing 80mg/ml of glucose – with a specific gravity of 1.026 is also available.

Mode of action:

Bupivacaine diffuses in its unchanged base form through neural sheaths and the axonal membrane to the internal surface of cell membrane Na⁺ channels .There they combine with hydrogen ions to form a cationic species, which enters the internal opening of the sodium channel and combines with the receptor. This produces the blockade of the sodium channel, thereby decreasing sodium ion conductance and preventing depolarization of the cell membrane.

Routes of Administration:

Bupivacaine may be administered topically, by infiltration, intrathecally or epidurally.

Anaesthetic Properties:

Bupivacaine is three to four times more potent than lidocaine or mepivacaine and eight times more potent than procaine. The duration of action of bupivacaine is 2-3 times longer than that of lidocaine or mepivacaine.

Onset and Duration of action:

The onset and duration of action of Bupivacaine varies according to the type of block.

Infiltration Anaesthesia

TABLE 4: ONSET AND DURATION OF ANALGESIA FOR BUPIVACAINE

Concentration	Plain		With epinephrine	
	Maximum dose (mg)	Duration (min)	Maximum dose (mg)	Duration (min)
0.25-0.5%	175	120-240	225	180

Nerve block

	Concentration	Volume (ml)	Dosage (mg)	Duration (min)	Onset (min)
Minor nerve block	0.25	5-20	12.5-50	180-360	
Major nerve block	0.25-0.5	30-50	225	360-720	15-30
epidural	0.25-0.75	15-30	37.5-22.5	180-300	10-20
spinal	0.5	3-4	15-20	75-200	
spinal	0.75	2-3	15-22.5		

Pharmacokinetics:**Pharmacokinetic properties:****TABLE 5: PHARMACOKINETIC PROPERTIES OF BUPIVACAINE**

T1/2 α (min)	T1/2 β (min)	Vdss (litres)	T1/2	Clearance(L/Min)
2.7	28	72	3.5	0.47

Absorption:

It can be detected in blood within 5 minutes of infiltration or following either epidural or intercostals nerve block. The absorption is proportionate to the vascularity of site of injection

The rate of absorption at different sites are as follows:

Intravenous>Tracheal>Intercostal>Caudal>Paracervical>Epidural>Brachial plexus>Sciatic>Subcutaneous.

A linear relationship exists between the total dose and the peak blood concentration achieved.

The presence of vasoconstrictors does not influence the rate of absorption of bupivacaine as the drug highly lipid soluble and therefore uptake into fat is rapid and the drug has direct vasodialatory effect.

Metabolism:

Bupivacaine is metabolized in the liver by N-dealkylation, primarily to pipecolyloxylyde.

N- desbutyl bupivacaine and 4-Hydroxy bupivacaine are formed.

Excretion:

Bupivacaine is mainly excreted in urine. 5% is excreted in the urine as pipecolyoxylidine and 16% is excreted unchanged.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This prospective, double blind, randomised controlled study intended to compare intrathecal 0.5% bupivacaine with 0.75% ropivacaine in urological surgeries (TURP) and URS after institutional ethical approval and after obtaining informed consent from the patients.

This study was undertaken in 142 patients in the age group from 18-80 years, ASA 1, 2& 3 scheduled for urological surgeries under spinal anaesthesia.

Patients with contraindication to spinal anaesthesia, patients who refused and patient with history of allergy to amide local anaesthetics were excluded from the study.

A thorough preoperative evaluation was done the day before surgery, laboratory investigations reviewed. Patient optimized for the preexisting illness. All patients were explained about the procedure and premedicated with oral pantoprazole 40mg and ondansetron 4mg.

The patients were randomly allocated into two groups of 71 each. Patients in group 1 received 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine (15mg) and patients in group 2 received 0.75% isobaric ropivacaine (15mg) through intrathecal route.

After shifting the patient to operation theater. IV access was secured with wide bore (20 G) IV cannula. Baseline heart rate, systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure and mean arterial pressure were recorded. Patients were positioned in lateral position.

Figure No 6 : Materials Used

Under strict asepsis and local anaesthesia lumbar puncture done at L3-L4 space using.

26 G Quincke's needle single prick midline approach, after confirming flow of clear CSF 0.5% bupivacaine (3ml) or 0.75% ropivacaine (2ml) injected intrathecally.

Patients were placed in supine position immediately. Anaesthesiologist who administered spinal anaesthesia was not further involved in observations.

After intrathecal injection sensory block assessed by loss of sensation by pin prick and motor block by modified Bromage scale. Surgery commenced when sensory block upto T10 segment was attained.

Modified Bromage scale:

Proposed by Bromage and modified by Cogan with Smith³⁷

Scale Criteria for motor block

TABLE No 6 : MODIFIED BROMAGE SCALE

Scale	Criteria	Degree & block
0	Free movement of legs, feet with ability to raise extended leg	None
1	Inability to raise extended leg and knee flexion is decreased but full extension of feet and ankle are present	Partial 33%
2	Inability to raise leg or flex knee, flexion of ankle and feet present	Partial 66%
3	Inability to raise leg, flex knee or ankle or movement toes.	Complete paralysis

All patients were kept in lithotomy during the procedure after which they were returned to supine. Continuous haemodynamic monitoring was done for 8hrs from time of block.

BP was recorded at every 1,5th min and 20th for 30 min after that every 15 minute interval till 60 minutes, every 60 minutes till 480 minutes. Changes of heart rate and rhythm were noted at the same interval.

In event of fall of heart rate >30% of baseline or <50 bpm and reduction in SBP >30% from baseline or SBP <100mmHg, it was treated with injection atropine 0.6mg and injection mephenteramine 3mg iv respectively The requirements of these drugs and duration of surgery recorded.

The end of study period was defined as the time at which the sensory block had regressed to below T10 dermatome and Bromage scale was 0.

Duration of motor block was defined as time from intrathecal injection to regression of motor block to Bromage score 0. Complete motor block was defined as Bromage score of 3.

Duration of complete motor block was defined as the time from intrathecal injection to regression of block to Bromage score of <3.

All patients had follow up visit on the day after the operation to look for full recovery of sensory and motor function and complication like nausea, vomiting, post dural puncture headache and transient neurological symptoms.

Statistical Methods

Descriptive statistical analysis has been carried out in the present study. Results of continuous measurements are presented on mean, standard deviation (Min-Max) and results of categorical measurements are presented in number (%). Significance was assessed at 5 % level of significance.

The quantitative data was analyzed using Unpaired Student t test.

Student's unpaired t test

$T = \frac{\text{Difference of means}}{\text{Standard error of difference of means}}$

The qualitative data was analyzed using Chi square test.

Chi square test:

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$$

O= Observed value, E= Expected value

* Moderately significant (P value: 0.01 < P < 0.05)

** Strongly significant (P value < 0.01)

Statistical software: The Statistical software namely SPSS 16.0 trial version was used for the analysis of the data and Microsoft word and Excel have been used to generate graphs and tables etc.

OBSERVATION AND RESULTS

A total of 142 patients were included in the study. They were allocated into two different groups of 71 each. Patients in group 1 received 3 ml of 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine (15 mg), while patients in group 2 received 2 ml of 0.75% isobaric ropivacaine through intrathecal route.

DEMOGRAPHIC DATA

The mean age of the patients in group 1 was 53.79 ± 13.66 years while in group 2 it was 59.39 ± 14.45 years and were comparable in both groups and was not significant statistically.

The mean height of the patients were 160.09 ± 8.69 cm and 159.45 ± 8.23 cm in group 1 and group 2 respectively and were comparable in both groups and was not significantly statistically.

The mean weight of the two groups were similar, while in group 1 it was 62.86 ± 8.83 Kg in group 2 it was 62.57 ± 6.60 Kg. It is statistically significant, clinically not significant.

The ASA physical status distribution was comparable in two groups. In group 1 34, 34 and 4 patients belonged to ASA 1, 2 and 3 respectively, while in group 2 the number of patients belonging to ASA 1, 2 and 3 were 32, 34 and 5 respectively.

Table No : 7

	Group 1			Group2			
Parameter	Mean	S.D	S.E	Mean	S.D	S.E	P-value
Age (yrs)	53.79	13.66	1.61	59.39	13.45	1.59	0.87
Height(cms)	160.09	8.69	1.02	159.45	8.23	0.97	0.54
Weight(kg)	62.86	8.83	1.04	62.57	6.60	0.78	0.0004*

Graph No 1 : Comparison of age height and weight.

Table No 8:

ASA Grade	Group				
	Group 1	Percentage	Group 2	Percentage	Total
1	34	47.88	32	45.07	65
2	34	47.88	34	47.88	68
3	03	4.22	05	7.05	09
Total	71	100	71	100	142

Graph No 2 : Percentage Distribution of patients according to ASA Grade.

Table No 9: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of patient according to Surgery Duration.

	Group 1		Group 2	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
27-40	29	40.8	30	42.2
40-50	35	49.2	28	39.4
50-60	7	10.0	13	18.4
Total	71	100	71	100

Graph No 3: Percentage Distribution of patient according to Surgery Duration.

Onset and regression of sensory block at T10

Onset of sensory blockade at T10 was achieved by 5.79 ± 1.38 minutes in patients in group 1 and 5.68 ± 1.57 minutes in patients of group 2. This was not clinically or statistically significant. All the patients attained a level of T10 sensory blockade in both the groups.

Table No 10 :

	Sensory Block at T10			
	Mean	S.D	S.E	P-value
Group 1	5.79	1.38	0.16	0.211
Group 2	5.68	1.57	0.188	

Graph No 4: Mean Sensory Block at T10

Highest level of sensory blockade:

All patients achieved a sensory block of T10 dermatome which was sufficient for surgery. Highest level of block achieved in group 1 was T6 in 47.8% of the patients compared to T6 in 60.57% of patients in group 2. There is no statistically significant difference between the two groups.

Table No 11: Highest sensory Block

Highest Sensory Block	Group 1		Group2		TOTAL
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	
T6	34	47.88	43	60.57	77
T7	14	19.71	18	25.36	32
T8	21	29.57	09	12.67	30
T10	02	2.84	01	1.40	03
TOTAL	71	100	71	100	142

Graph no 5- Highest sensory block

Time from injection to two dermatomal regression:

Time from injection to two dermatomal regression was 129.54±15.68 minutes in group 1 and 111.31±22.69 minutes in group 2, when compared it was found to be highly significant statistically with a P value of <0.001.

Time required for sensory level to regress below T10:

When the time required for sensory level to regress below T10 dermatomal level was studied it was found to be 178.76±16.34 minutes for group 1 and 172.20±14.8 minutes for group 2 which is statistically not significant as P-value is 0.1 (P>0.05 NS).

Table No 12: Time from injection to two dermatomal regression.

	Two dermatomal regression.			
	Mean	S.D	S.E	P-value
Group 1	129.54	15.68	1.85	0.0001*
Group 2	111.31	22.69	2.71	

Table No 13: Time required sensory level to regress below T10.

	Sensory level to regress below 10.			
	Mean	S.D	S.E	P-value
Group 1	178.76	16.34	1.92	0.44
Group 2	172.20	14.28	1.70	

Graph No 6: Regression of Sensory Block

Onset and duration of motor block:

The mean time required for the onset of Bromage score of 1 in patients belonging to group 1 was 4.59 ± 1.25 minutes while that for patients in group 2 was 6.30 ± 1.44 minutes. The results were clinically and statistically highly significant with P-value of <0.001 .

Table No 14 : Bromage Scale in groups

	Bromage Scale			P-value
	Mean	S.D	S.E	
Group 1	4.59	1.25	0.15	$<0.0001^*$
Group 2	6.30	1.44	0.18	

Graph no 7- bromage scale

Mean duration of motor block:

The mean duration of motor block in group 1 patients was 198.27±18.60 minutes while that of group 2 was 133.74±17.64 minutes which was not statistically significant as P-value is >0.001.

Mean duration of complete motor block:

The mean duration of complete motor block in group 1 patients was 169.29±17.80 minutes while that of group 2 was 108.98±9.58 minutes which was clinically and statistically highly significant as P-value is <0.001.

Table No15: duration of motor blockage *

	Duration of motor blockage			
	Mean	S.D	S.E	P-value
Group 1	198.27	18.60	2.19	0.417
Group 2	133.74	17.64	2.10	

Table No 16: Duration of complete motor block

	Duration of complete motor block			
	Mean	S.D	S.E	P-value
Group 1	169.29	17.80	2.09	<0.0001*
Group 2	108.98	9.58	1.14	

Graph No 8: Comparison of duration complete motor block

HAEMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

All the haemodynamic parameters e.g. heart rate, systolic blood pressure (SBP), diastolic blood pressure (DBP) and mean arterial pressure (MAP) were monitored 1,5 and 20 minutes first 30 minutes, 40 and 60th min for next 30 minutes and every 60 minutes for next 480 minutes.

There was no significant change in mean heart rate in either of the two groups statistically or clinically. No patients in either of two groups had bradycardia.

Mean systolic pressure showed a stastically significant decrease from preblock values at 5 minutes with P value 0.038 between two groups.

Mean diastolic blood pressure showed a statistically significant decrease from preblock values at 5 minutes with a P- value of 0.008 between the two groups.

Mean arterial pressure did not show any statistically significant decrease.

Table No 17 : Hemodynamic parameters

		Mean	S.D	S.E	P-value
Basal	Group1	77.8611	6.80784	.80231	0.520
	Group2	78.4143	6.16792	.73721	
1 Min	Group1	74.2222	6.79524	.80083	0.055
	Group2	76.0429	5.36612	.64137	
5 Min	Group1	73.3194	6.38622	.75262	0.137
	Group2	71.0143	5.14005	.61435	
20 Min	Group1	71.7222	5.46750	.64435	0.157
	Group2	70.6286	4.38764	.52442	
40 Min	Group1	72.5556	5.60405	.66044	0.124
	Group2	73.9857	3.49531	.41777	
60Min	Group1	73.0556	4.90441	.57799	0.781
	Group2	73.7429	3.18368	.38052	
120 Min	Group1	73.1667	4.45004	.52444	0.154
	Group2	74.7714	3.58811	.42886	
180 Min	Group1	73.4861	4.04897	.47718	0.281
	Group2	74.0429	4.17180	.49863	
240 Min	Group1	74.6944	4.41712	.52056	0.229
	Group2	74.8429	3.99505	.47750	
300 Min	Group1	73.8333	4.12823	.48652	0.925
	Group2	74.0000	4.40026	.52593	
360 Min	Group1	74.1389	4.76875	.56200	0.053
	Group2	74.7000	4.16107	.49734	
420 Min	Group1	74.4167	4.14440	.48842	0.132
	Group2	74.3714	3.85299	.46052	
480 Min	Group1	74.1250	4.19570	.49447	0.245
	Group2	75.7857	2.32125	.27744	

Graph no 9 Comparison of heart rate

Table No 18 : Systolic Blood Pressure

		Mean	S.D	S.E	P-value
SBP	Group1	132.7778	17.66848	2.08225	0.663
	Group2	131.0000	15.49848	1.85242	
1 Min	Group1	125.0278	15.03046	1.77136	0.879
	Group2	124.4286	15.32978	1.83226	
5 Min	Group1	114.1667	11.89982	1.40241	0.038*
	Group2	124.2817	14.60448	1.73323	
20 Min	Group1	116.6111	12.44996	1.46724	0.103
	Group2	116.7714	10.02196	1.19785	
40 Min	Group1	117.7222	13.09685	1.54348	0.177
	Group2	115.2286	10.49661	1.25459	
60Min	Group1	119.5278	12.88516	1.51853	0.663
	Group2	116.8286	11.02037	1.31719	
120 Min	Group1	120.3611	11.30039	1.33176	0.727
	Group2	116.8857	10.61929	1.26925	
180 Min	Group1	118.4167	11.29845	1.33153	0.277
	Group2	117.6571	9.28749	1.11007	
240 Min	Group1	125.8611	15.56206	1.83401	0.08
	Group2	124.5070	21.07054	2.50061	
300 Min	Group1	121.6667	9.22336	1.08698	0.931
	Group2	119.2857	10.04936	1.20113	
360 Min	Group1	121.7500	7.84309	.92432	0.076
	Group2	120.1429	8.04568	.96164	
420 Min	Group1	123.8056	7.68507	.90569	0.218
	Group2	122.6286	6.85707	.81958	
480 Min	Group1	125.9722	8.28025	.97584	0.205
	Group2	122.4000	8.04048	.96102	

Graph No 10: Comparison of Systolic Blood Pressure

Table no 19 : Comparison of Diastolic Blood Pressure

DBP	Groups	Mean	S.D	S.E	P-value
Basal	Group1	79.6667	5.65685	.66667	0.412
	Group2	80.2286	6.51903	.77917	
1 Min	Group1	77.3611	6.63602	.78206	0.838
	Group2	77.1429	6.73792	.80534	
5 Min	Group1	73.5000	7.36761	.86828	0.008*
	Group2	76.2286	5.82392	.69609	
20 Min	Group1	71.3333	7.33888	.86490	0.541
	Group2	74.6571	6.54723	.78254	
40 Min	Group1	73.6389	8.03041	.94639	0.941
	Group2	74.6000	7.91513	.94604	
60Min	Group1	76.9722	6.97677	.82222	0.522
	Group2	76.9714	7.06691	.84466	
120 Min	Group1	76.7500	5.44822	.64208	0.138
	Group2	76.4000	6.32089	.75549	
180 Min	Group1	75.9444	6.10677	.71969	0.624
	Group2	77.6000	5.88390	.70326	
240 Min	Group1	75.6944	6.23177	.73442	0.08
	Group2	75.2857	5.06234	.60507	
300 Min	Group1	78.1667	5.56397	.65572	0.725
	Group2	76.4857	6.25484	.74760	
360 Min	Group1	79.2500	5.28018	.62227	0.095
	Group2	77.1429	4.66341	.55738	
420 Min	Group1	81.2500	4.50899	.53139	0.570
	Group2	79.4857	4.16592	.49792	
480 Min	Group1	82.1389	5.85579	.69011	0.240
	Group2	79.2000	6.30068	.75308	

Graph No 11: Comparison of Diastolic Blood Pressure

TABLE NO 20: COMPARISION OF MEAN BP

MEAN BP	Group	Mean	S.D	S.E	P-value
Basal	Group1	97.2333	9.53820	1.12409	0.659
	Group2	97.0157	8.97736	1.07300	
1 Min	Group1	93.1639	8.77413	1.03404	0.930
	Group2	92.9114	8.97589	1.07282	
5 Min	Group1	88.4875	8.92060	1.05130	0.100
	Group2	92.1800	8.17007	.97651	
20 Min	Group1	86.3944	8.16005	.96167	0.150
	Group2	99.2157	87.78520	10.49234	
40 Min	Group1	89.0333	9.98912	1.17723	0.063
	Group2	87.2914	6.95863	.83172	
60Min	Group1	91.3431	8.56443	1.00933	0.059
	Group2	95.5257	10.28344	1.22911	
120 Min	Group1	91.3139	5.94224	.70030	0.281
	Group2	90.3043	7.21802	.86272	
180 Min	Group1	90.5583	5.98031	.70479	0.441
	Group2	90.6271	6.52293	.77964	
220 Min	Group1	90.2125	6.64612	.78325	0.062
	Group2	90.8129	5.97228	.71382	
300 Min	Group1	92.5806	5.74014	.67648	0.883
	Group2	91.0571	7.04070	.84152	
360 Min	Group1	93.2681	4.63908	.54672	0.564
	Group2	91.5243	4.97651	.59481	
420 Min	Group1	95.3097	4.74324	.55900	0.442
	Group2	93.6229	4.42251	.52859	
480 Min	Group1	96.4944	6.11866	.72109	0.592
	Group2	93.6614	6.09184	.72811	

Graph No 12: Comparison of Mean Blood Pressure

COMPLICATIONS:

None of the patients of group 1 or group 2 had any incidence of bradycardia. 30 patients of group 1 and 13 patients of group 2 had hypotension, which was treated with a bolus of injection mephenteramine 3 mg.

Table No 21 :

Mephentermine (mg)	Group 1		Group 2		P-value
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	
0	42	58.3	57	81.4	0.007*
3	28	38.9	14	18.6	
6	1	2.8	0	00	
Total	72	100	70	100	

Graph No 13 : Frequency Of Inj Mephentaramine (Hypotension)

No patients of either group complained of nausea and vomiting.

There was no incidence of post dural puncture headache or transient neurological symptoms in either of the 2 groups.

DISCUSSION

Subarachnoid block is commonly employed regional anaesthetic technique for performing transurethral resection of prostate and URS. It provides adequate anaesthesia for the patient and good relaxation of the pelvic floor and the perineum for the surgeon.

The signs and symptoms of water intoxication and fluid overload can be recognized early because the patient is awake. Accidental bladder perforation is also recognized easily if the spinal level is limited to T10 because the patient experiences abdominal or shoulder pain.

Satisfactory regional anaesthesia for TURP and URS involves achieving block level that interrupts sensory transmission from the prostate and bladder neck, lower ureter.

Bupivacaine remains one of the most popular local anaesthetic agents because of its high potency and minimal neurological symptoms but caution is required because of its toxicity profile particularly to the cardia. Though cardiotoxicity is not of concern in subarachnoid blockade, the quality of sensory blockade, duration of motor blockade, haemodynamic changes and side effect profile are some consideration in selecting a drug for spinal anaesthesia.

Ropivacaine is pure 'S' enantiomer³⁸ of local anaesthetic. Because of sensory motor dissociation, ropivacaine could be a favourable local anaesthetic for day-care

surgery and could be associated with early postoperative mobilization than bupivacaine.

Advantages claimed are shorter duration of motor block¹⁹ with similar sensory block properties compared to bupivacaine (McDonald SB)²¹. It minimizes the psychological discomfort of being immobile for long time. Although its major advantage is less cardiotoxic^{9,20} property compared to bupivacaine.

The primary aim of our study was to compare the relative anaesthetic effects of 0.75% isobaric ropivacaine and 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine. This study was conducted to assess the sensory and motor characteristics of ropivacaine for spinal anaesthesia in Endoscopic urological surgeries (TURP and URS).

A prospective randomized controlled, double blind study was done at Shri BM Patil medical college and research centre involving 142 patients of ASA grade 1, 2, and 3 who underwent endoscopic urological surgeries (TURP and URS) under spinal anaesthesia.

Onset of sensory block at T10:

All patients receiving either drug achieved adequate level of anaesthesia up to T10. We considered sensory block at T10 was adequate for performing TURP and URS (for lower ureteric calculi) surgeries.

Chan- Jong Chung²⁶ and colleagues used 18mg of hyperbaric ropivacaine for caesarean delivery and found that onset time of block to T10 was 3.2min. In our study, we noted that mean time for onset at T10 was 5.79 (4.41-7.17) min with bupivacaine and 5.68 (4.11-7.25) min with 15 mg ropivacaine which is comparable to

a study conducted by Y. Y. Lee³⁹ et al in urological surgeries, wherein the onset time of block to T10 was 5-7.5 min for bupivacaine and 2.5-9.4 minutes for ropivacaine.

Mac Namee³⁹ and colleagues used 3.5 ml of 5 mg/mL (17.5 mg) isobaric ropivacaine for total hip arthroplasty and found to have a median onset time of 2 min (2-5 min). J.F. Luck²⁵ and colleagues found no significant differences between the three groups with respect to times. Median range to time of analgesia to pinprick at T10 for bupivacaine was 2-5 min, levobupivacaine was 2-15 min and ropivacaine was 2-15 min.

Highest level of sensory block:

Gautier et al²⁹ used plain preparation of bupivacaine and ropivacaine, compared the extent of sensory block and concluded that extent of sensory block were similar. In our study, we noted highest level of sensory block was similar between the two groups which was comparable to studies done by McDonald²¹ and colleague, C. O. Ogun³⁰ and Y. Y. Lee³⁹.

Time from injection to two dermatomal regression:

J. F. Luck²⁵ and colleagues observed that the times of sensory block regression, both to T10 [bupivacaine 129min (58–178min), levobupivacaine 131min (50–205min), and ropivacaine 84min (45–145min)] and complete regression were shorter in the ropivacaine group than other two groups. We also observed that two dermatomal regression with ropivacaine was faster compared to bupivacaine and this augers well with results of above mentioned study. Y. Y. Lee³⁹ et al also observed time from injection to two dermatomal regression was 69-149 min in ropivacaine group and 97-143 min in bupivacaine group.

Time to regression of sensory block to below T10:

Y. Y. Lee et al³⁹ observed that time to regression of sensory block to below T10 was 141-211 min in ropivacaine group and 154-209 min in bupivacaine group. Chan Jong Chung²⁶ and others noted that time of regression of block to S1 was longer (188.56±28.2min) in bupivacaine group when compared to ropivacaine group (162.56 ±20.2 min). In our study results were comparable in both the groups and this concurs with observation of Kim S Khaw et al.⁴⁰ who noted that regression to S1 was comparable when either intrathecal isobaric ropivacaine or bupivacaine was used

Onset time to Bromage score of 1:

Y.Y. Lee et al³⁹ observed that onset time to Bromage score of 1 was 2.5-6.3 min for bupivacaine and 2.5-9.4 min for ropivacaine. M. Mantouvaloy²⁷ noted that mean time of onset to achieve Bromage score 1 with bupivacaine was 2±1 min, ropivacaine 3±1 min and levobupivacaine 2±1min. P.Gautieret al²⁹, compared the effects of intrathecal bupivacaine (8mg), levobupivacaine (8mg), ropivacaine(12mg), for caesarean section and found that the mean time for onset of Gr3 Bromage motor block was 9min and 14min for bupivacaine and ropivacaine respectively.

We noticed that the mean time for onset of motor blockade to Bromage score of 1 was 4.59±1.25 min with bupivacaine and 6.30±1.44 min with ropivacaine. In our study, patients receiving ropivacaine had delayed onset of motor blockade compared to bupivacaine, this is in agreement with the above mentioned studies.

Duration of motor block:

S. Sanli⁴¹ et al noted that duration of motor blockade was 118 min with 15 mg isobaric ropivacaine when used for caesarean section. Y. Y. Lee et al³⁹ . observed

that duration of motor block was shorter in ropivacaine group (93-162 min) compared with bupivacaine group (157-234 min). In our study, duration of motor blockade was 198.27 ± 18.60 min for bupivacaine while that of ropivacaine was 133.74 ± 18.64 min.

We observed a shorter duration of motor blockade with ropivacaine compared to bupivacaine. Our findings are in affirmation with that of Chan Jong Chung²⁶ and colleagues, J. K. Luck²⁵ and Helena Kallio¹⁸ and others who also found shorter duration (120min) of motor blockade with ropivacaine when compared to bupivacaine. Kim S. Khaw⁴⁰ and colleagues also noted shorter duration of motor block with 15mg of ropivacaine for caesarean section.

Duration of complete motor block:

Y. Y. Lee et al.³⁹ noted that the duration of complete motor block was shorter in ropivacaine group (63-120 min) when compared with bupivacaine group (126-183 min). D. A. Mcnamee²⁴ observed that duration of complete motor block was significantly prolonged in ropivacaine 10 mg/mL compared with ropivacaine 7.5 mg/mL (1.9 hrs Vs 1.2 hrs). Chan Jong Chung²⁶ and colleagues also observed duration of complete motor blockade was 90-135 min for ropivacaine group and 105-225 min for bupivacaine group.

In our study it was 169.29 ± 17.80 min in bupivacaine group and 108.98 ± 9.58 ropivacaine group

Quality of anaesthesia and muscle relaxation:

The anaesthesia was well accepted by surgeons and blinded anaesthesiologist belonging to both groups. Majority opined that the quality of anaesthesia and relaxation is good to excellent with both the drugs.

Hemodynamic parameters:

Montouvalou et al.²⁷ used isobaric solutions of ropivacaine and bupivacaine for lower abdominal surgeries and concluded that intraoperative hypotension requiring treatment occurred more in bupivacaine group 42.5% than in ropivacaine group 25%.

In our study hypotension occurred in 41.7% of patients in group 1 and 18.6% of patients in group 2 comparable to above mentioned study. None of the patients in both groups had bradycardia. Haemodynamic parameters including heart rate, systolic blood pressure were comparable between the two groups but diastolic and mean arterial pressure at 5 min showed statistically significant difference but the difference was 5 mmHg which is clinically insignificant. Incidence of hypotension was comparable in both groups, which was easily managed by mephenteramine bolus.

Complications:

Incidence of nausea and vomiting was comparable between the two groups. There was no incidence of post dural puncture headache, transient neurological symptoms in either of the two groups.

CONCLUSION

Our study reveals that 15 mg of isobaric ropivacaine (2 mL of 0.75%) when administered intrathecally provides adequate anaesthesia for endoscopic urological surgeries. Onset of sensory blockade and highest level of sensory block is similar to that of bupivacaine, while two dermatomal regression is significantly faster with ropivacaine. There is a delayed onset of motor block and the duration of motor block is shorter with ropivacaine compared to bupivacaine.

With the above characteristics and safer haemodynamic and side effect profile ropivacaine is a suitable drug for intrathecal usage in endoscopic urological surgeries.

SUMMARY

A prospective randomized controlled double blind study was conducted involving 142 patients belonging to ASA grade 1, 2 & 3 undergoing endoscopic urological surgeries (TURP and URS). They were randomly divided into 2 groups of 71 each. Group 1 received 3mL of 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine, group 2 received 2mL of 0.75% isobaric ropivacaine. Following institution of subarachnoid block sensory characteristics such as onset of sensory block, highest level of block, time from injection to two dermatomal regression and time to regression of sensory block to below T10 were studied. Motor blockade characteristics such as onset of motor block, duration of motor blockade and complete motor blockade were studied. Haemodynamic parameters like heart rate, SBP, DBP and MAP were monitored every 1,5 and 20 min interval for first 30 min after that every 20 minute interval till 60 minutes, every 60 minutes till 480 minutes. Incidence of side effects such as hypotension, bradycardia, nausea, vomiting, PDPH and transient neurological symptoms were noted.

Results were analysed using student unpaired t test and chi square test. Demographic parameters in both groups were comparable. Onset of sensory block and time to regression of sensory block to below T10 was comparable in both groups. Highest level of sensory block was comparable between both groups. Time from injection to two dermatomal regression was shorter in ropivacaine group. Onset of motor block to Bromage score 1 was slower, duration of motor blockade and duration of complete motor blockade was also shorter with ropivacaine compared to

bupivacaine. However all the patients in either groups attained complete motor blockade. Haemodynamic parameters were comparable in both the groups with magnitude of fall in blood pressure being similar. Incidence of side effects such as hypotension, bradycardia and nausea & vomiting were comparable in both the groups.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Brown DL. Spinal block in Atlas of Regional Anaesthesia. 2nd edition. WB Saunders Company, Philadelphia; 1999.
2. George A Albright. Cardiac arrest following regional anaesthesia with Ethidocaine and Bupivacaine- Editorial Views. The Journal of Anesthesiology. 1979; 51:285-287.
3. Moller R, Cavoni B. Cardiac electrophysiologic effects of Lidocaine and Bupivacaine. Anaesth Analg 1988; 67:107-109.
4. Charles B Berde, Gary R Strichartz. Local anesthetics. Miller's anaesthesia. 7th edition. Churchill Livingstone Elsevier, New York 2010;913-936.
5. J. B Whiteside, J. A. W. Wildsmith. Developments in local anesthetic drugs Br J Anaesth 2001; 87(1):27-35.
6. Friedman G A, Rowlingson J C, Difazio C A, Donegan M F. Evaluation of the analgesic effect and urinary excretion of systemic Bupivacaine in man. Anaesth Analg 1982; 61:23-27.
7. Yamashino H, Yokihitho C. Bupivacaine induced seizure after accidental intravenous injection & complication of epidural anaesthesia. Anesthesiology 1977; 47:472-473.
8. Clarkson C W, Hondeghem C. M. Mechanism for bupivacaine depression of cardiovascular conduction: Fast block of sodium channels during the action potential with slow recovery from block during diastole. Anesthesiology 1985;62:396-405.
9. Feldman H S, Arthur G R, Pitkaun M, Hurley R, Ducette A M, Cavino B G. Treatment of acute systemic toxicity after the rapid intravenous injection of

- Ropivacaine and Bupivacaine in the Conscious dog. *Anaesth Analg* 1991; 73:373-384.
10. Vanhutte F, Verecke J, Verbeke N, Carmeliet E. Stereoselective effects of enantiomers of Bupivacaine on electrophysiological properties of guinea-pig papillary muscle. *Br J Pharmacol* 1991; 103:1275-1281.
 11. McClure J H. Ropivacaine. *Br J Anaesth* 1996; 76:300-307.
 12. Jeffery A Katz, Phillip O Bridenbaugh, Donna C, Sally H Helton, Donald D Denson. Pharmacodynamics and Pharmacokinetics of Epidural Ropivacaine in Humans. *Anaesth Analg* 1990; 70:16-21.
 13. Scott D B, Lee A, Fagan D, Bowler G M R, Bloom field P, Lundh R. Acute toxicity of Ropivacaine compared with that of Bupivacaine. *Anaesth Analg* 1989; 69:563-569.
 14. L M Morrison, B M Emmanuelsson, J H McClure, A J Pollock, D W McKeown, M Brockway, et al. Efficacy and kinetics of extradural Ropivacaine comparison with Bupivacaine. *Br J Anaesth* 1994;72:164-169.
 15. M S Brockway, J Bannister, J H McClure, D W McKeown, J A W Wildsmith. Comparison of Extradural Ropivacaine and Bupivacaine. *Br J Anaesth.* 1991;66:31-37.
 16. Edward Crosby, Alan Saudler, Brenden Finucane, Besmond Writer, Dennis Reid, Jocelyne McKenna et al. Comparison of epidural anaesthesia with Ropivacaine 0.5% and Bupivacaine 0.5% for Caesarean section. *Can J Anaesth* 1998; 45:1066-1071.
 17. A P Wolff, L Hassoltrom, H E Kerkkup, M J Gielen. Extradural Ropivacaine and Bupivacaine in Hip surgery. *Br J Anaesth* 1995; 74:458-460.

18. Helena Kallio, Eljas-Veli T Snall, Markku P Kero, Per H Rosenberg. A comparison of intrathecal plain solutions containing Ropivacaine 20 or 15 mg versus Bupivacaine 10 mg. *Anaesth Analg* 2004;99:713–7.
19. Cpogna G, Cellono D, Fusco P, Lyons G, Columb M. Relative potencies of bupivacaine and ropivacaine for analgesia in labor. *Br J Anaesth.* 1999; 82:371-3
20. Yamashita A, Matsumoto M, Matsumoto S, Itoh M, Kawai K, Sakabe T. A comparison of the neurotoxic effects on the spinal cord of tetracaine, lidocaine, bupivacaine, and ropivacaine administered intrathecally in rabbits. *Anesth Analg* 2003; 97:512- 9.
21. Susan B McDonald, Spencer S Liu, Dan J Kopacz, Carol A Stephenson. Hyperbaric spinal Ropivacaine a comparison to Bupivacaine in volunteers. *Anesthesiology* 1999; 90:971-7.
22. Andrea Casati, Elena Moizo, Chiara Marchetti, Federico Vinciguerra. A Prospective, randomized, double-blind comparison of unilateral spinal anaesthesia with hyperbaric Bupivacaine, Ropivacaine, or Levobupivacaine for inguinal herniorrhaphy. *Anesth Analg* 2004; 99:1387–92.
23. Osama Al-Abdulhadi, Diane Biehl, Bill Ong, Adulaziz Boker. Hyperbaric spinal for elective cesarean section Ropivacaine Vs Bupivacaine. *Middle East J Anesthesiol* 2007; 9:385-397.
24. D A McNamee, A M McClelland, S Scott, K R Milligan, G Westman, U Gustafsson. Spinal anaesthesia: Comparison of plain Ropivacaine 5mg/mL with Bupivacaine 5 mg/mL for major orthopaedic surgery. *Br J Anaesth* 2002; 89:702-6.

25. J F Luck, P D W Fettes, J A W Wildsmith. Spinal anaesthesia for elective surgery: A comparison of hyperbaric solutions of racemic Bupivacaine, Levobupivacaine, and Ropivacaine. *Br J Anaesth.* 2008; 101:705–10.
26. Chan-Jong Chung, So-Ron Choi, Kwang-Hwan Yeo, Han Suk Park, Soo-Il Lee, Young- Jhoon Chin. Hyperbaric spinal Ropivacaine for caesarean delivery: A comparison to hyperbaric Bupivacaine. *Anaesth Analg* 2001; 93:157-161.
27. Mantouvalou M, Ralli S, Arnaoutoglou H, Tziris G, Papadopoulos G. Spinal anaesthesia: Comparison of plain Ropivacaine, Bupivacaine and Levobupivacaine for lower abdominal surgery. *Acta Anaesthesiol Belg* 2008; 59:65-71.
28. Jean-Marc Malinovsky, Florence Charles, Ottmar Kick, Jean-Yves Lepage, Myriam Malinge, Antoine Cozian, et al. Intrathecal anaesthesia: Ropivacaine versus Bupivacaine. *Anaesth Analg* 2000; 91:1457-1460.
29. P Gautier, M De Kock, L Huberty, T Demir, M Izydorczic, B Vanderick. Comparison of the effects of intrathecal Ropivacaine, Levobupivacaine, and Bupivacaine for Caesarean section. *Br J Anaesth.* 2003;91:684-689.
30. Ogun C O, Kirgiz E N, Duman A, Okesil S, Akyurek C. Comparison of intrathecal isobaric Bupivacaine-Morphine and Ropivacaine-Morphine for Caesarean delivery. *Br J Anaesth* 2003; 90:659-664.
31. Neval Boztug, Zekiye Bigat, Bilge Karsli, Nurdan Saykal, Ertugrul Ertok. Comparison of Ropivacaine and Bupivacaine for intrathecal anaesthesia during outpatient arthroscopic surgery. *J Clin Anesth* 2006; 18:521–525.
32. David L Brown. Spinal, epidural and caudal anesthesia. *Miller's Anesthesia.* 7th edition: Churchill Livingstone Elsevier, New York 2010; 1611-1638.

33. Christopher M Bernards. Epidural and Spinal Anesthesia. Clinical anaesthesia. 6th edition. Wolters Kluwer Lippincott Williams & Wilkins, New York 2009; 927-950.
34. Willium F Ganong. Physiology of central nervous system. Review of Medical Physiology. 22nd edition. Lange Medical book 2005; 556 574.
35. Prys Roberts C, Brown B R. Local Anaesthetic Pharmacology. International Practice of Anaesthesia. 1st edition. Oxford Butterworth, Heinmsnn 1996.
36. Anathony M Akham, Diana Faulds. Ropivacaine: Review of its pharmacology and therapeutics use in regional anaesthesia. Drugs 1996; 52:429-449.
37. Collens V J. Local anesthetics. Principle of anesthesiology. Philadelphia Lea and Fabiger 1983; 1259-1262.
38. Brendon T F, Alan N S, Joceylene M, Dennis R, Anna-Lee M, Mark F, et al. A double-blind comparison of ropivacaine 0.5%, 0.75%, 1.0%, injected epidurally in patients undergoing abdominal hysterectomy. Can J Anaesth 1996; 43: 442-9.
39. Lee Y Y, Ngan Kee W D, Fong S Y, Liu J T, Gin T. The Median effective dose of bupivacaine, levobupivacaine and ropivacaine after intrathecal injection in lower limb surgery. Anesth Analg 2009 ; 109:1331-4.
40. Kim S Khaw, Warwick D Ngan Kee, Mabel Wong, Floria Ng, Anna Lee. A Dose-finding Study of Spinal Ropivacaine for Cesarean Section. Anesthesiology 2001; 95:1346–50.
41. Sanli S, Yegin A, Kayacan N, Yilmaz M, Coskunfirat N, Karsli B. Effects of hyperbaric spinal ropivacaine for caesarean section: with or without fentanyl. Eur J Anaesthesiol 2005; 22:457-461

ANNEXURES

PROFORMA

COMPARISON OF 0.5% HYPER BARIC BUPIVACAINE AND 0.75% ISOBARIC ROPIVACAINE FOR SPINAL ANAESTHESIA IN ENDOSCOPIC UROLOGICAL SURGERIES

NAME : Ht in cm:

Group 1: hyperbaric 0.5% bupivacaine 15 mg

AGE/SEX: Wt in kg:

Group 2: Isobaric 0.75% ropivacaine 15 mg

IP NO.:

ASA grade:

SURGERY:

1. Duration of surgery:

SUBARACHNOID BLOCK:

- Space:
- Position:
- Onset of sensory block to T10(min):
- Highest level of sensory block:
- Time to two segment regression(min):
- Time to regression of sensory block below T10(min):
- Onset time to Bromage score 1(min):

➤ *duration of motor block(min):

MODIFIED BROMAGE SCALE

Scale	Criteria
0	free movement of legs, feet with ability to raise extended leg
1	Inability to raise extended leg and knee flexion is decreased but full extension of feet and ankle are present
2	Inability to raise leg or flex knee, flexion of ankle and feet present
3	Inability to raise leg, flex knee or ankle or movement toes

**duration of complete motor block(min):

* Time from intrathecal injection to regression of motor block to Bromage score 0.

** Time from intrathecal injection to regression of motor block to Bromage score <3

HEMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

In minutes	basal	1	5	20	40	60	120	180	240	300	360	420	480
Hr BPM													
SBP mmhg													
DBP mmhg													
MAP mmhg													

Hypotension: Y/N

IV Mephentramine:

(SBP >30% Baseline)

Bradycardia(<50/min) : Y/N

COMPLICATIONS:

1. Nausea/Vomiting:
2. Transient neurological symptoms:
3. Post dural puncture headaches

STUDY SUBJECT CONSENT STATEMENT

I confirm that Dr. Abhishek Rao Kordcal., has explained to me the purpose of this research, the study procedure that I will undergo and the possible discomforts and benefits that I may experience, in my own language.

I have been explained all the above in detail in my own language and I understand the same. Therefore I agree to give my consent to participate as a subject in this research project.

(Participant)

Date

(Witness to above signature)

Date

B.L.D.E. UNIVERSITY'S
SHRI.B.M.PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, BIJAPUR-586 103
INSTITUTIONAL ETHICAL COMMITTEE

INSTITUTIONAL ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

The Ethical Committee of this college met on 20-10-2011 at 10-30 am to scrutinize the Synopsis/Research projects of postgraduate/undergraduate student/Faculty members of this college from Ethical Clearance point of view. After scrutiny the following original/corrected & revised version synopsis of the Thesis/Research project has been accorded Ethical Clearance.

Title "Intraaethcal Ropivalaine Vs Bugivalaine in endoscopic urological surgeries"

Name of P.G./U.G. student/Faculty member Dr. Abhishek Rao Kordcar
Dept of Anesthesiology

Name of Guide/Co-investigator Dr. V.T. Kalyanappa
Dept of Anesthesiology

DR.M.S.BIRADAR,
CHAIRMAN
INSTITUTIONAL ETHICAL COMMITTEE
BLDEU'S, SHRI.B.M.PATIL
MEDICAL COLLEGE, BIJAPUR.
Chairman
Ethical Committee
BLDEA'S Shri. B.M. Patil
Medical College
Bijapur-586103

Following documents were placed before E.C. for Scrutinization

- 1) Copy of Synopsis/Research project.
- 2) Copy of informed consent form
- 3) Any other relevant documents.

KEY TO MASTER CHART

IP no : In patient number

Ht : Height

cm : Centimeter

wt : Weight

kg : Kilogram

ASA : American society of anaesthesiologist

Min : Minute

mg : Milligram

BP : Blood pressure

Sys : Systolic

Dia : Diastolic

SL. No	Name	Age	ip No	ht in cm	wt in kg	Group	ASA grade	Surgery duration	sensory block at 10	Highest sensory block	2 dermatomal regression	regression of sensory block below t 10	Bromage scale 1	Duration of motor blockade	duration of complete motor blockade	heart rate nasal	1 min	5 min	20 min	40 min	60 min	120 min	180 min	240 min	300 min	360 min	420 min	480 min	in/ atropine in mg	basal systolic bp	basal Diastolic bp	Basal mean bp	Sys1 min	Dia 1 min	mean 1 min	5 min sys	5 min dia	5 min mean	20 min sys	20 min dia	20 min mean	40 min sys	
1	parsappa	55	9478	167	65	1	1	30	6	101	156	3	200	130	86	75	74	77	78	80	76	72	75	73	78	79	75	0	136	84	101.3	116	78	90.6	110	72	84	104	74	84	114		
2	chandrankanth	22	9191	169	63	1	1	37	7	6	120	180	5	190	145	76	70	72	74	79	71	70	75	77	73	78	79	72	0	150	80	103.3	148	80	102.6	110	78	96	116	74	88	118	
3	parmana	69	9462	172	65	1	2	33	5	7	132	190	6	170	155	80	77	70	72	68	69	70	71	75	76	79	80	74	0	160	90	113.3	140	86	104	110	84	102	120	70	86.6	136	
4	prakash	60	9130	154	68	1	1	45	8	8	154	200	4	176	176	72	67	68	70	65	70	73	72	71	69	70	74	72	0	140	80	100	110	70	83.3	106	70	82	98	60	72.6	110	
5	allappa	88	8906	168	52	1	3	50	5	6	128	168	2	210	187	68	64	70	66	66	70	71	71	72	73	69	70	70	0	130	80	96.6	110	70	88.3	108	66	80	122	88	99.3	114	
6	gouri	27	8944	167	68	1	1	32	6	8	110	172	7	230	198	78	70	72	73	79	80	71	74	75	75	73	75	77	0	130	80	96.6	142	88	106	112	76	96	116	66	82.6	122	
7	ashwat	62	8645	167	54	1	2	48	4	10	142	178	5	222	189	76	72	74	76	75	78	78	70	74	76	71	72	74	0	110	70	83.3	118	84	95.3	100	86	96	110	72	84.6	132	
8	allauddin	80	8919	174	53	1	3	54	3	8	121	200	4	189	187	64	60	62	58	64	65	62	63	66	65	61	64	65	0	116	72	86.6	108	64	78.6	100	60	73.3	100	62	74.6	96	
9	shantayya	42	8236	172	77	1	1	36	6	8	136	202	6	190	167	88	82	80	74	82	73	78	77	81	75	77	79	81	0	140	82	101.3	132	70	90.6	118	66	83.3	110	68	82	116	
10	govind	52	8457	163	76	1	1	40	7	7	141	189	5	220	156	84	80	80	79	79	80	81	79	82	80	78	79	77	83	0	140	80	100	138	84	102	120	78	92	126	78	94	110
11	sureka	40	8329	158	75	1	2	53	6	6	107	176	4	237	167	80	77	78	75	77	76	79	80	74	78	79	77	77	0	136	82	100	128	78	94.6	110	78	95.3	110	76	87.3	110	
12	hajisab	50	2409	152	67	1	1	28	5	6	121	208	7	180	178	76	76	74	70	73	78	79	74	76	74	79	77	74	0	120	82	94.6	108	76	86.6	104	64	77.3	112	70	84	118	
13	dyamanna	43	2863	148	54	1	2	41	4	8	133	195	4	178	146	72	70	68	77	71	72	70	73	74	73	75	76	75	0	140	86	104	142	84	103.3	110	80	101.3	140	78	98.6	130	
14	ravi	55	2290	158	53	1	1	44	3	6	158	165	5	196	164	84	80	81	80	85	78	77	76	79	74	77	79	80	0	180	90	120	152	84	106.3	112	78	102	150	80	103.3	150	
15	banu	64	2371	156	59	1	2	50	6	6	102	148	3	170	130	86	85	82	80	74	78	76	77	78	80	81	80	84	0	110	70	83.3	104	72	82.6	108	74	85.3	98	60	72.6	98	
16	basavaraj	65	2343	143	66	1	2	29	6	8	111	154	6	230	178	70	68	64	61	65	64	68	70	67	65	69	70	71	0	130	80	96.6	128	82	97.3	122	76	91.3	118	76	90	102	
17	babu	65	2078	145	50	1	2	35	7	6	132	167	5	210	186	77	75	72	67	70	72	75	76	78	73	72	70	73	0	140	86	104	138	80	99.3	126	82	96.6	116	70	85.3	110	
18	durgappa	68	1863	153	57	1	2	38	9	7	127	172	4	207	190	90	87	88	79	72	76	74	78	79	71	70	74	75	0	156	84	108	140	80	100	130	84	103.3	122	74	90	110	
19	gundappa	65	665	161	57	1	2	42	6	6	131	183	3	189	168	72	70	68	71	68	66	68	70	71	77	74	72	71	0	156	82	106.6	140	80	100	122	86	104.6	128	64	85.3	142	
20	mangala	68	655	160	59	1	2	47	5	8	156	156	6	178	177	80	78	76	70	69	70	71	72	74	76	77	75	72	0	130	80	96.6	122	78	92.6	120	76	90.6	110	70	83.3	118	
21	kashibai	64	659	152	53	1	2	50	7	8	134	187	6	192	188	86	83	78	71	73	71	73	74	78	75	73	71	76	0	130	80	96.6	110	70	83.3	108	66	80	122	88	99.3	114	
22	rudrappa	61	1356	163	56	1	1	53	7	7	129	176	5	175	180	69	65	60	57	59	60	62	61	60	61	60	64	65	0	130	80	96.6	142	88	106	122	76	96	116	66	82.6	122	
23	renuka	57	27751	172	76	1	1	40	5	6	143	174	5	211	168	78	75	74	72	76	74	70	71	74	76	70	71	74	0	110	70	83.3	118	84	95.3	116	86	96	110	72	84.6	132	
24	mukalal	65	311664	163	77	1	3	42	5	6	138	209	4	226	178	74	71	70	70	73	74	76	79	80	71	74	75	76	0	116	72	86.6	108	64	78.6	110	60	73.3	100	62	74.6	96	
25	chandappa	32	27764	169	74	1	1	45	5	7	128	182	5	220	162	76	72	70	70	72	76	78	79	80	78	76	73	74	0	130	80	104	104	72	82.6	108	74	85.3	110	68	82	116	
26	amarappa	66	17722	158	75	1	1	47	7	6	105	201	5	200	165	77	74	75	75	71	78	76	72	70	72	77	72	76	0	140	82	101.3	132	70	90.6	100	66	83.3	116	70	85	126	
27	ratnabai	65	16916	152	67	1	2	48	4	7	125	176	4	178	159	82	80	84	71	78	78	74	75	75	78	79	76	75	0	110	72	83.3	128	80	96	112	76	90.6	118	76	90	116	
28	amarappa	55	16899	148	54	1	1	50	5	6	131	167	3	198	164	86	84	76	68	72	74	75	75	74	75	71	72	70	0	116	82	86.6	100	68	78.6	98	64	75.3	112	74	86.6	114	
29	balram	61	16708	165	53	1	1	56	5	6	147	156	6	190	170	84	80	78	76	78	70	70	78	76	80	80	81	82	0	140	80	101.3	112	74	86.6	114	76	88.6	118	76	91.3	126	
30	gowrawwa	56	15431	168	67	1	1	27	6	8	134	154	5	187	165	70	68	66	71	71	76	77	75	78	73	72	77	79	0	140	82	100	118	78	91.3	110	78	90.6	98	60	72.6	110	
31	ramesh	65	348714	170	67	1	1	32	7	6	123	192	6	196	188	84	80	76	78	76	77	78	74	79	80	74	76	79	0	136	82	100	118	70	83.3	106	70	82	98	60	72.6	98	
32	imahammed	65	15819	143	56	1	2	33	5	6	119	190	4	199	167	70	70	68	71	71	70	72	71	71	78	74	75	70	0	120	86	94.6	104	72	82.6	108	74	85.3	112	70	84	118	
33	deranna	65	15818	154	50	1	2	43	5	6	108	179	6	213	188	74	70	68	68	72	77	79	73	75	74	72	71	72	0	140	90	104	108	76	86.6	104	64	77.3	116	66	82.6	122	
34	aravind	70	15774	158	72	1	2	47	6	8	149	165	3	178	130	77	74	71	69	70	71	77	74	74	72	76	71	70	0	180	70	120	142	88	106	100	76	96	118	76	90	116	
35	keshav rao	56	15343	160	70	1	1	46	6	6	152	180	3	208	156	89	85	80	72	76	74	70	78	76	74	77	75	74	0	110	80	83.3	100	68	78.6	98	64	75.3	126	64	84.6	130	
36	shivalingayya	65	17489	148	54	1	2	30	6	6	101	156	3	200	130	86	75	74	77	78	80	76	72	75	73	78	79	75	0	140	80	100	132	70	90.6	100	84	102	126	76	92.6	134	
37	anarkali	30	17553	158	53	1	2	37	7	6	120	180	5	190	145	76	70	72	74	79	71	70	75	77	73	78	79	72	0	130	80	96.6	138	84	102	106	70	82	116	66	82.6	136	
38	shivagamma	50	15836	156	59	1	1	38	9	7	127	172	4	207	190																												

SL. No	Name	Age	Ip No	ht in cm	wt in kg	Group	ASA grade	Surgery duration	sensory block at 10	Highest sensory block	2 dermatomal regression	regression of sensory block below t 10	Bromage scale 1	Duration of motor blockade	duration of complete motor blockade	heart rate nasal	1 min	5 min	20 min	40 min	60 min	120 min	180 min	240 min	300 min	360 min	420 min	480 min	in/ atropine in mg	basal systolic bp	basal Diastolic bp	Basal mean bp	Sys1 min	Dia 1 min	mean 1 min	5 min sys	5 min dia	5 min mean	20 min sys	20 min dia	20 min mean	40 min sys
46	mailayya	58	8072	172	76	1	2	47	7	6	105	201	5	200	165	77	74	75	75	71	78	76	72	70	72	77	72	76	0	140	80	100	140	80	100	118	66	83.3	98	60	72.6	118
47	balappa	55	7556	163	77	1	2	48	4	7	125	176	4	178	159	82	80	84	71	78	78	74	75	75	78	79	76	75	0	136	82	100	122	78	92.6	120	78	92	118	76	90	130
48	neelappa	56	7512	169	74	1	1	50	5	6	131	167	3	198	164	86	84	76	68	72	74	75	75	74	75	71	72	70	0	120	82	94.6	104	72	82.6	132	78	95.3	112	70	84	110
49	veeresh	50	7516	158	75	1	2	30	6	6	101	156	3	200	130	86	75	74	77	78	80	76	72	75	73	78	79	75	0	140	86	104	128	82	97.3	104	64	77.3	140	78	98.6	110
50	rajasab	62	2514	152	67	1	1	37	7	6	120	180	5	190	145	76	70	72	74	79	71	70	75	77	73	78	79	72	0	180	90	120	138	80	99.3	144	80	101.3	150	80	103.3	138
51	seema	75	7842	148	54	1	2	33	5	7	132	190	6	170	155	80	77	70	72	68	69	70	71	75	76	79	80	74	0	110	70	83.3	140	80	100	150	78	102	98	60	72.6	130
52	rajappa	30	3881	165	53	1	1	45	8	8	154	200	4	176	176	72	67	68	70	65	70	73	72	71	69	70	74	72	0	130	80	96.6	140	80	100	108	74	85.3	118	76	90	150
53	shanta	40	3201	167	65	1	2	50	5	6	128	168	2	210	187	68	64	70	66	66	70	71	71	72	73	69	70	70	0	120	82	94.6	122	78	92.6	122	76	91.3	116	70	85.3	98
54	kamala	40	2403	169	63	1	1	32	6	8	110	172	5	230	198	78	70	72	73	79	80	71	74	75	75	73	75	77	0	140	86	104	110	70	88.3	110	72	84	122	74	90	102
55	sachin	52	2401	172	65	1	2	48	4	10	142	178	5	222	189	76	72	74	76	75	78	78	70	74	76	71	72	74	0	180	90	120	142	88	106	132	78	96	128	64	85.3	110
56	basappa	55	6357	154	68	1	3	54	3	8	121	200	4	189	187	64	60	62	58	64	65	62	63	66	65	61	64	65	0	110	70	83.3	118	84	95.3	138	84	102	110	70	83.3	114
57	bhimash	75	5785	168	52	1	1	36	6	8	136	202	6	190	167	88	82	80	74	82	73	78	77	81	75	77	79	81	0	130	80	96.6	108	64	78.6	106	70	82	122	88	99.3	118
58	itabai	55	7140	167	68	1	2	40	7	7	141	189	5	220	156	84	80	80	79	79	80	81	79	82	80	78	77	83	0	140	86	104	104	72	82.6	108	66	80	116	66	82.6	136
59	laxmibai	60	7511	167	54	1	2	53	6	6	107	176	4	237	167	80	77	78	75	77	76	79	80	74	78	79	79	77	0	156	84	108	116	78	90.6	136	76	96	122	74	90	110
60	sandeep	29	6876	174	53	1	2	28	5	6	121	208	7	180	178	76	76	74	70	73	78	79	74	76	74	79	77	74	0	156	82	106.6	148	80	102.6	116	86	96	128	64	85.3	114
61	sushilabai	40	6793	172	77	1	1	41	4	8	133	195	4	178	146	72	70	68	77	71	72	70	73	74	73	75	76	75	0	130	80	96.6	140	86	104	100	60	73.3	110	70	83.3	122
62	vijay	54	6785	163	76	1	2	44	3	6	158	165	5	196	164	84	80	81	80	85	78	77	76	79	74	77	79	80	0	130	80	96.6	110	70	83.3	118	66	83.3	122	88	99.3	132
63	bajappa	45	6787	158	75	1	2	50	6	6	102	148	3	170	130	86	85	82	80	74	78	76	77	78	80	81	80	84	0	130	80	96.6	110	70	83.3	120	78	92	116	66	82.6	96
64	hanmappa	34	6783	152	67	1	2	29	6	8	111	154	6	230	178	70	68	64	61	65	64	68	70	67	65	69	70	71	0	110	70	83.3	142	88	106	132	78	95.3	110	72	84.6	116
65	madivalappa	34	6367	147	69	1	1	35	7	6	132	167	5	210	186	77	75	72	67	70	72	75	76	78	73	72	70	73	0	116	72	86.6	118	84	95.3	116	78	90.6	100	62	74.6	110
66	bhagappa	58	5952	161	54	1	2	38	9	7	127	172	4	207	190	90	87	88	79	72	76	74	78	79	71	70	74	75	0	140	82	101.3	108	64	78.6	106	70	82	110	68	82	110
67	vimalabai	60	5954	155	68	1	1	42	6	6	131	183	3	189	168	72	70	68	71	68	66	68	70	71	77	74	72	71	0	110	72	83.3	132	70	90.6	108	74	85.3	116	70	85	118
68	fatima	30	5956	172	76	1	2	47	5	8	156	156	6	178	177	80	78	76	70	69	70	71	72	74	76	77	75	72	0	116	82	86.6	138	84	102	104	64	75.3	120	70	86.6	130
69	manjunath	52	4746	161	65	1	1	45	8	8	154	200	4	176	176	72	67	68	70	65	70	73	72	71	69	70	74	72	0	140	80	101.3	128	78	94.6	136	76	96	98	60	72.6	150
70	raziya	40	11276	148	54	1	2	33	5	7	132	178	5	222	189	76	72	74	74	79	71	70	75	77	73	78	79	72	0	130	80	96.6	132	70	90.6	108	74	85.3	122	88	99.3	98
71	shreshail	45	21509	165	53	1	1	45	8	8	154	200	4	189	187	64	60	62	72	68	69	70	71	75	76	79	80	74	0	110	70	83.3	138	84	102	122	76	91.3	116	70	85	102
72	ravi	59	5336	167	59	2	1	50	5	6	128	168	2	210	187	68	64	70	66	66	70	71	71	72	73	69	70	70	0	140	82	100	108	76	86.6	98	64	75.3	142	78	99.3	132
73	bhimappa	75	5785	168	73	2	3	41	3	6	85	146	9	98	76	82	80	78	74	70	75	74	73	77	76	74	70	78	0	130	80	96.6	142	76	98	138	74	95.3	116	70	85	126
74	bhimappa	82	14905	161	61	2	2	58	6	7	76	158	10	140	87	75	70	68	74	79	74	73	76	78	79	75	74	78	0	138	76	96.6	156	92	113.3	142	86	104.6	120	66	84	128
75	jayamma	68	15076	162	54	2	3	51	5	8	94	178	7	134	98	68	65	64	54	61	60	63	58	59	60	61	62	65	0	118	74	88.6	142	82	102	144	84	104	130	80	96	138
76	jayamma	73	15070	149	58	2	1	34	7	10	102	164	6	156	101	72	70	70	69	73	72	71	70	74	78	71	72	74	0	114	78	90	128	80	96	120	76	90.6	114	66	82	114
77	irasangayya	60	15303	148	72	2	1	36	9	6	123	180	5	145	116	87	83	80	79	76	75	78	74	76	79	77	78	74	0	110	70	83.3	136	74	94.6	130	70	90	118	76	90	116
78	irayya	62	15197	162	57	2	3	38	10	6	132	160	8	176	104	62	80	56	59	60	61	60	62	64	60	61	62	70	0	122	84	96.6	140	80	100	140	80	100	112	74	86.6	114
79	siddappa	72	13804	161	70	2	2	28	5	7	99	157	4	154	105	78	74	70	76	78	75	79	73	72	71	72	75	72	0	126	80	95.3	136	78	97	130	70	90	96	70	78.6	104
80	wishwanath	69	15028	153	77	2	3	48	6	7	107	174	3	164	120	79	77	70	72	77	73	71	76	78	74	76	75	78	0	160	90	113.3	100	68	78.6	98	64	75.3	120	86	97.6	122
81	shalilaja	77	14476	167	56	2	1	52	4	8	135	176	6	100	114	86	89	80	72	74	76	77	74	77	73	76	77	74	0	150	90	110	112	74	86.6	114	76	88.6	118	76	91.3	126
82	sanganabasu	55	14605	148	62	2	2	31	8	6	154	206	7	110	106	90	84	80	76	75	74	76	75	79	75	73	76	74	0	130	80	96.6	106	74	84.6	100	72	81.3	138	82	100.6	130
83	gangadhar	68	15024	159	53	2	3	35	7	6	148	186	8	124	98	87	85																									

SL. No	Name	Age	Ip No	ht in cm	wt in kg	Group	ASA grade	Surgery duration	sensory block at 10	Highest sensory block	2 dermatomal regression	regression of sensory block below t 10	Bromage scale 1	Duration of motor blockade	duration of complete motor blockade	heart rate nasal	1 min	5 min	20 min	40 min	60 min	120 min	180 min	240 min	300 min	360 min	420 min	480 min	in/ atropine in mg	basal systolic bp	basal Diastolic bp	Basal mean bp	Sys1 min	Dia 1 min	mean 1 min	5 min sys	5 min dia	5 min mean	20 min sys	20 min dia	20 min mean	40 min sys
91	ramanna	68	13329	167	59	2	2	41	5	6	100	198	8	111	119	75	74	70	74	73	77	73	76	75	78	71	74	78	0	148	84	103.3	114	66	82	122	74	90	112	74	86.6	114
92	bhimray	80	13787	143	55	2	1	48	4	6	98	165	6	123	115	74	78	70	70	71	74	73	77	78	75	74	70	76	0	170	90	117.3	130	80	96.6	126	80	95.3	96	70	78.6	104
93	arjun	60	13335	154	65	2	2	52	5	8	102	177	6	135	107	72	71	68	70	77	70	70	72	75	73	74	76	77	0	160	90	113.3	100	68	78.6	98	64	75.3	120	86	94.6	122
94	bhagyashree	76	13188	148	67	2	1	58	7	7	107	182	5	140	113	82	80	75	70	77	73	77	70	77	73	76	79	75	0	132	80	97.3	112	74	86.6	114	76	88.6	118	76	91.3	126
95	sidappa	55	13027	164	57	2	2	30	5	6	137	160	6	146	109	72	70	65	68	75	74	79	74	76	79	77	74	76	0	128	76	93.3	132	70	90.6	140	76	93.3	110	68	82.1	106
96	sabamma	50	12843	162	72	2	1	31	6	6	86	176	7	122	123	84	81	76	76	76	72	74	75	72	70	78	76	79	0	130	80	96.6	106	74	84.6	100	72	81.3	114	66	82	114
97	rafeeq	54	12825	172	63	2	1	33	8	6	72	165	6	122	116	88	83	80	70	70	77	75	74	75	73	78	75	76	0	138	76	96.6	120	80	94.6	128	78	100.6	120	86	97.6	122
98	sateema	52	12024	170	58	2	1	43	7	8	109	156	8	107	110	76	72	70	70	74	76	74	73	79	77	75	73	78	0	118	74	88.6	118	78	91.3	116	78	90.6	98	60	72.6	98
99	veerabadrappa	52	12484	162	58	2	2	39	5	6	121	163	4	105	114	74	70	65	70	70	74	72	78	75	73	77	72	76	0	114	78	90	114	66	82	122	74	90	110	68	82	116
100	kiran	65	12320	161	56	2	2	36	5	6	140	189	3	132	106	70	71	67	68	76	73	73	75	74	78	75	77	73	0	110	70	83.3	136	78	97	130	70	90	118	76	91.3	126
101	faridsab	76	12003	153	68	2	2	49	4	7	122	190	7	128	110	78	75	70	70	76	74	79	73	76	68	75	77	74	0	122	84	96.6	120	80	94.6	128	78	100.6	118	76	90	116
102	salima	76	12024	167	64	2	1	44	6	6	117	148	6	156	111	80	76	70	75	72	77	79	81	80	78	83	75	78	0	126	80	95.3	104	72	82.6	108	74	85.3	96	70	78.6	104
103	gangamma	62	11996	153	62	2	2	52	5	6	69	175	8	144	118	86	84	76	65	78	73	70	78	75	74	76	78	74	0	160	90	113.3	132	70	90.6	118	66	83.3	110	70	83.3	118
104	mallappa	72	11314	158	56	2	1	43	4	7	77	161	6	135	100	87	85	76	63	76	75	73	78	73	79	77	74	80	0	150	90	110	118	78	91.3	116	78	90.6	142	78	99.3	130
105	shantayya	58	11985	164	57	2	2	30	5	6	137	160	6	146	109	72	70	65	68	75	74	79	74	76	79	77	74	76	0	130	80	96.6	100	68	78.6	98	64	75.3	116	70	85	128
106	shivanagouda	71	11877	150	69	2	1	35	6	6	120	186	7	125	96	76	74	74	74	76	79	74	74	73	77	79	76	74	0	114	78	90	106	74	84.6	100	72	81.3	120	66	84	94
107	gopal	56	8285	153	70	2	2	46	7		101	170	6	116	88	84	70	67	68	76	73	78	74	77	73	76	78	75	0	110	70	83.3	122	78	92.6	120	76	90.6	120	86	97.6	106
108	ramakrishnappa	75	306065	167	56	2	1	47	7	6	123	187	7	130	110	74	76	70	70	71	70	76	73	77	76	74	70	78	0	122	84	96.6	108	64	78.6	114	76	88.6	118	76	91.3	96
109	shivalingayya	65	17489	148	62	2	1	48	4	7	133	176	6	137	117	78	78	70	74	76	73	77	76	78	79	75	74	78	0	126	80	95.3	104	72	82.6	100	72	81.3	138	82	100.6	116
110	aishwarya	68	5390	159	53	2	2	34	3	7	131	165	5	143	123	72	70	65	76	70	78	76	58	59	60	61	62	77	0	160	90	113.3	116	78	90.6	128	78	100.6	130	84	99.3	114
111	suvarna	38	4892	172	56	2	1	56	9	8	119	187	5	156	108	86	80	80	70	74	76	73	70	74	78	71	72	75	0	150	90	110	148	80	102.6	116	78	90.6	120	78	92	104
112	umabai	59	4597	163	57	2	1	29	8	6	89	192	7	164	103	79	75	70	71	76	72	74	74	76	79	77	78	73	0	130	80	96.6	140	86	104	144	84	104	118	70	86	122
113	anandappa	48	4894	147	69	2	1	41	6	6	100	198	8	111	119	75	74	70	74	73	77	73	72	74	76	61	62	76	0	150	86	107.7	110	70	83.3	140	80	100	118	72	87.3	126
114	mallappa	50	4896	161	54	2	1	48	4	6	98	165	6	123	115	74	78	70	70	71	74	73	73	72	71	72	75	73	0	126	80	95.3	110	70	83.3	128	76	93.3	114	68	83.3	106
115	sakamma	63	4836	155	68	2	2	52	5	8	102	177	6	135	107	72	71	68	70	77	70	70	76	78	74	76	75	76	0	122	80	94	142	88	106	132	80	97.3	110	68	82	126
116	bhimashi	70	4888	172	76	2	2	58	7	7	107	182	5	140	113	82	80	75	70	77	73	77	74	77	73	76	77	76	0	130	64	82.6	118	84	95.3	140	78	94	110	70	83.3	106
117	girijabai	40	4597	161	65	2	2	30	5	6	137	160	6	146	109	72	70	65	68	75	74	79	73	72	71	72	75	78	0	150	82	104.6	108	64	78.6	138	86	98	118	76	90	114
118	abdul	58	4595	167	59	2	1	31	6	6	86	176	7	122	123	84	81	76	76	76	72	74	76	78	74	76	75	78	0	118	74	88.6	132	70	90.6	144	84	104	112	74	86.6	122
119	vilas	45	4591	143	55	2	2	36	5	6	140	189	3	132	106	70	71	67	68	76	73	73	74	77	73	76	77	74	0	114	78	90	138	84	102	140	80	100	96	70	78.6	98
120	siddanna	63	4922	154	65	2	2	49	4	7	122	190	7	128	110	78	75	70	70	76	74	79	75	79	75	73	76	77	0	122	84	96.6	128	78	94.6	128	76	93.3	120	86	94.6	116
121	kallappa	61	4599	148	67	2	1	44	6	6	117	148	6	156	111	80	76	70	75	72	77	79	77	75	74	78	79	75	0	110	70	83.3	108	76	86.6	132	80	97.3	114	66	82	114
122	sharanappa	40	4411	164	57	2	2	52	5	6	69	175	8	144	118	86	84	76	65	78	73	70	78	72	79	75	76	78	0	122	84	96.6	142	76	98	126	78	94	118	76	90	104
123	gurappa	60	4185	162	72	2	1	43	4	7	77	161	6	135	100	87	85	76	63	76	75	73	74	77	75	79	76	76	0	126	80	95.3	156	92	113.3	122	86	98	112	74	86.6	122
124	kenchappa	63	4325	172	63	2	1	30	5	6	137	160	6	146	109	72	70	65	68	75	74	79	75	72	70	78	73	77	0	150	90	110	142	82	102	122	74	90	96	70	78.6	126
125	amatappa	62	26922	170	58	2	1	35	6	6	120	186	7	125	96	76	74	74	74	76	79	74	75	79	75	73	76	75	0	160	90	113.3	104	72	82.6	126	80	95.3	120	86	97.6	106
126	appu rathod	35	26810	162	58	2	1	46	7		101	170	6	116	88	84	70	67	68	76	73	78	77	75	74	78	79	76	0	150	90	110	128	82	97.3	98	64	75.3	118	76	91.3	114
127	mallamma	48	25349	161	56	2	1	47	7	6	123	187	7	130	110	74	76	70	71	70	76	78	72	79	75	76	79	0	130	80	96.6	138	80	99.3	114	76	88.6	138	82	100.6	122	
128	bapugowda	32	26054	153	68	2	2	48	4	7	133																															

SL. No	Name	Age	Ip No	ht in cm	wt in kg	Group	ASA grade	Surgery duration	sensory block at 10	Highest sensory block	2 dermatomal regression	regression of sensory block below t 10	Bromage scale 1	Duration of motor blockade	duration of complete motor blockade	heart rate nasal	1 min	5 min	20 min	40 min	60 min	120 min	180 min	240 min	300 min	360 min	420 min	480 min	inj atropine in mg	basal systolic bp	basal Diastolic bp	Basal mean bp	Sys 1 min	Dia 1 min	mean 1 min	5 min sys	5 min dia	5 min mean	20 min sys	20 min dia	20 min mean	40 min sys
138	jakawwa	45	10250	143	55	2	2	52	5	6	69	175	8	144	118	86	84	76	65	78	73	70	74	76	73	79	73	75	0	126	80	95.3	140	86	104	144	84	104	118	70	86	126
139	sidappa	38	10595	154	65	2	2	43	4	7	77	161	6	135	100	87	85	76	63	76	75	73	76	75	78	71	74	76	0	126	80	95.3	110	70	83.3	142	76	90.6	120	86	106	
140	santosh	42	2464	148	67	2	2	30	5	6	137	160	6	146	109	72	70	65	68	75	74	79	77	78	75	74	70	75	0	150	86	107.3	110	70	83.3	130	70	90	114	66	82	126
141	ramanagouda	70	2521	164	57	2	1	44	6	6	117	148	6	156	111	80	70	67	68	76	73	78	72	75	73	74	76	78	0	126	80	95.3	108	76	86.6	140	80	100	118	76	90	106
142	rudragouda	68	4143	162	72	2	2	52	5	6	69	175	8	144	118	86	76	70	70	71	70	76	70	77	73	76	79	73	0	112	80	94	128	82	97.3	144	84	104	112	74	86.6	114

	40 min dia	40 min mean	60 min sys	60 min dia	60 min mean	120 min sys	120 min dia	120 min mean	180 min sys	180 min dia	180 min mean	240 min sys	240 min dia	240 min mean	300 min sys	300 min dia	300 min mean	360 min sys	360 min dia	360 min mean	420 min sys	420 min dia	420 min mean	480 min sys	480 min dia	480 min mean	inj mephetermine in mg	nausea / vomiting	transient neurological symptoms	post dural puncture headache
70	86	122	82	95.3	114	76	88.6	118	76	90	128	78	94.6	134	86	102	114	86	95.3	122	86	98	128	76	93.3	3	0	0	0	
78	95.3	128	86	101	118	72	87.3	124	80	94.6	132	88	102.6	128	86	100	118	82	94	122	86	98	112	68	82.6	0	0	0	0	
60	76.6	118	78	83.3	116	78	90.6	116	80	92	112	68	82.6	120	82	94.6	128	84	98.6	114	78	90	134	90	105	3	0	0	0	
76	87.3	118	78	83.3	128	72	90.6	128	78	94	100	70	80	128	70	89.3	114	82	92.6	110	70	83.3	128	76	93.3	0	0	0	0	
70	86	124	84	100	146	70	95.3	120	84	96	120	82	94.6	138	80	99.3	120	78	92	130	86	100.6	112	68	82.6	0	0	0	0	
78	95.3	114	72	86	100	76	84	118	78	91.3	128	78	94.6	116	76	89.3	128	78	94.6	130	74	92	134	90	105	0	0	0	0	
74	99.3	92	70	77.3	114	78	90	110	74	86	132	88	102.6	122	76	91.3	122	78	92.6	120	80	93.3	120	84	96	0	0	0	0	
60	78	114	74	87.3	134	86	102	112	72	85.3	112	68	82.6	124	84	97.3	128	84	98.6	120	86	97.3	116	78	90.6	0	0	0	0	
78	86	118	80	92.6	128	76	93.3	110	76	87.3	134	78	96.6	128	64	85.3	132	88	102.6	116	84	94	128	78	94.6	0	0	0	0	
70	83.3	110	76	87.3	110	70	83.3	102	76	84.6	144	78	100	128	82	97.3	134	86	102	128	78	94	132	78	96	3	0	0	0	
70	84.6	120	78	92	116	82	93.3	128	84	98.6	114	70	84.6	134	86	102	118	82	94	140	82	101	120	86	97	3	0	0	0	
68	84.6	140	80	100	116	74	88	122	72	88.6	118	74	88.6	128	86	100	128	74	92	116	80	92	136	86	102	3	0	0	0	
78	97.3	114	72	86	128	74	92	120	78	92	126	80	95.3	120	82	94.6	116	72	86.6	122	86	98	136	86	103	3	0	0	0	
70	83.3	122	86	96	100	70	80	110	62	78	128	82	97.3	128	70	89.3	122	86	98	122	86	98	122	84	96.6	0	0	0	0	
74	87.3	118	80	92.6	130	86	101	120	78	92	108	70	82.6	138	80	99.3	126	68	87.3	114	78	90	112	68	82.6	0	0	0	0	
86	98	130	90	103	114	76	88.6	110	62	78	116	72	92.6	116	76	89.3	136	86	102.6	110	70	83.3	134	90	105	3	0	0	0	
86	101	90	64	75.3	120	84	96	132	68	89.3	108	70	82.6	122	76	91.3	118	76	90	130	86	100.6	120	84	96	0	0	0	0	
62	73.3	122	82	95.3	122	78	92.6	150	72	98	114	70	84.6	128	82	97.3	114	82	92.6	136	88	104	116	78	90.6	3	0	0	0	
76	89.3	120	68	88	122	78	92.6	108	72	84	112	68	82.6	124	84	97.3	110	74	86	130	80	96.6	128	78	94.6	3	0	0	0	
60	76.6	122	82	95.3	136	76	96	100	86	98	110	70	83.3	128	64	85.3	112	86	94.6	118	78	91.3	140	86	104	0	0	0	0	
76	87.3	120	68	88	128	84	98.6	118	76	90	180	78	91.5	128	82	97.3	128	76	93.3	138	86	103.3	132	84	100	0	0	0	0	
70	86	114	70	84.6	116	82	93.3	124	80	94.6	122	80	94	128	64	85.3	126	70	88.6	130	80	96.6	116	76	89.3	3	0	0	0	
78	95.3	114	74	87.3	116	74	88	130	74	92.3	124	74	90.6	128	82	97.3	128	78	94.6	120	82	94.6	140	90	107	0	0	0	0	
74	99.3	134	70	91.3	128	74	92	130	86	100.6	120	80	93.3	112	78	89.3	136	80	98.6	130	74	92	136	82	100	0	0	0	0	
60	78	148	76	100	100	70	80	110	74	86	124	86	98.6	116	78	90.6	114	86	95.6	120	80	93.3	122	88	99.3	3	0	0	0	
78	86	118	80	92.6	130	86	101	102	76	84.6	128	86	100	128	82	97.3	118	76	90	120	86	97.3	124	82	96	0	0	0	0	
72	92	132	74	109	130	70	90	130	72	91.3	122	70	89.3	134	82	99.3	136	80	98.6	130	82	98	128	80	96	0	0	0	0	
84	98	128	86	101	130	90	103	132	88	102	130	72	88.6	128	76	93	126	70	88.6	130	74	92	132	78	96	0	0	0	0	
78	94	120	70	100	124	72	89.3	128	78	94	136	80	96.6	128	78	94.6	126	78	94	130	80	96.6	132	84	100	0	0	0	0	
86	103	136	80	103	130	84	99	106	86	102	180	90	105.3	140	86	104	134	80	98	138	86	103	140	80	100	0	0	0	0	
64	80.6	110	70	107	100	66	77.3	134	68	80	180	76	90	120	70	86.6	116	74	88	120	84	96	122	86	98	0	0	0	0	
74	88	118	78	83.3	112	70	84	106	76	90	108	78	91.5	116	80	92	120	78	92	120	80	93.3	118	86	90	3	0	0	0	
70	84.6	118	78	83.3	122	76	91.3	120	80	93.3	110	70	82.6	112	74	86.6	112	72	85	120	86	97.3	122	88	99.3	0	0	0	0	
76	95.3	108	78	86.6	100	68	78.6	120	68	80	110	70	83.3	114	76	88.6	120	80	93.3	118	78	91.3	110	70	83.3	3	0	0	0	
84	90	110	80	97.3	108	84	95.3	104	86	87.3	116	76	95.3	118	84	95.6	120	82	92.3	128	78	92.6	126	76	95.3	0	0	0	0	
82	93.3	124	84	100	118	80	96.6	122	80	97.3	132	72	92.6	114	74	94	120	76	86.6	116	76	87.3	118	78	90.6	0	0	0	0	
72	91.3	128	84	113	124	80	94.6	128	82	97.3	120	88	102.6	136	90	105.3	134	84	100.6	134	86	102	132	84	100	0	0	0	0	
82	98.6	138	86	115	130	84	99.3	124	78	93.3	180	72	88	118	70	86	136	70	88.6	136	86	102.6	134	88	103	0	0	0	0	
74	88	116	78	96.6	118	76	90	114	74	87.3	132	74	88.6	120	76	90.6	116	74	88	118	78	91.3	116	76	89.3	0	0	0	0	
84	99.3	122	76	109	126	76	92.3	124	74	90.6	126	80	97.3	136	84	101.3	130	82	98	126	80	95.3	122	82	95.3	0	0	0	0	
76	93.3	132	82	98.6	134	80	94.6	130	84	99.3	122	78	94	128	76	93.3	124	82	96	128	76	93.3	126	78	94	0	0	0	0	
58	70	90	56	100	118	70	84.3	120	74	89.3	118	72	88.6	126	74	91.3	128	76	93.3	128	74	92	122	70	97.3	3	0	0	0	
70	82	114	66	84.6	116	74	88	116	74	88	94	72	87	114	76	88	108	74	95.3	114	72	86	116	70	85.3	0	0	0	0	
60	72	98	62	100	100	70	80	102	74	83.3	118	68	76.6	96	62	73.3	98	62	74	118	76	90	106	70	82	3	0	0	0	
74	88	118	78	83.3	112	70	84	120	76	90	108	78	91.5	116	80	92	120	78	92	120	80	93.3	118	86	90	0	0	0	0	

	40 min dia	40 min mean	60 min sys	60 min dia	60 min mean	120 min sys	120 min dia	120 min mean	180 min sys	180 min dia	180 min mean	240 min sys	240 min dia	240 min mean	300 min sys	300 min dia	300 min mean	360 min sys	360 min dia	360 min mean	420 min sys	420 min dia	420 min mean	480 min sys	480 min dia	480 min mean	inj mephetermine in mg	nausea / vomiting	transient neurological symptoms	post dural puncture headache
70	84.6	118	78	83.3	122	76	91.3	120	80	93.3	110	70	82.6	112	74	86.6	112	72	85	120	86	97.3	122	88	99.3	0	0	0	0	
76	85.3	108	78	86.6	100	68	78.6	104	68	80	110	70	83.3	114	76	88.6	120	80	93.3	118	78	91.3	110	70	83.3	3	0	0	0	
84	90	110	80	97.3	108	84	95.3	114	86	87.3	116	76	95.3	118	84	95.6	120	82	95.6	120	78	92.6	126	76	95.3	0	0	0	0	
82	93.3	124	84	100	118	80	96.6	112	80	97.3	118	72	92.6	114	74	94	120	76	94	120	76	87.3	118	78	90.6	0	0	0	0	
70	82	114	66	84.6	116	74	88	116	74	88	180	72	87	114	76	88	108	74	88	108	72	86	116	70	85.3	0	0	0	0	
64	80.6	110	70	107	100	66	77.3	106	68	80	110	76	90	120	70	86.6	116	74	86.6	116	84	96	122	86	98	0	0	0	0	
84	90	110	80	97.3	108	84	95.3	104	86	87.3	114	76	95.3	118	84	95.6	120	82	95.6	120	78	92.6	126	76	95.3	0	0	0	0	
60	78	92	70	77.3	100	76	84	108	72	84	120	70	84.6	116	76	89.3	118	82	89.3	118	82	94.6	122	88	99.3	3	0	0	0	
76	89.3	122	82	95.3	130	86	101	128	84	98.6	116	82	94.6	122	78	92.3	128	76	92.6	128	86	100.6	128	78	94.6	0	0	0	0	
82	93.3	124	84	100	118	80	96.6	122	80	97.3	118	72	92.6	114	74	94	120	76	94	120	76	87.3	118	78	90.6	0	0	0	0	
74	88	118	78	83.3	112	70	84	120	76	90	110	78	91.5	116	80	92	120	78	92	120	80	93.3	118	86	90	3	0	0	0	
76	85.3	108	78	86.6	100	68	78.6	104	68	80	122	70	83.3	114	76	88.6	120	80	88.6	120	78	91.3	110	70	83.3	3	0	0	0	
84	95.3	116	80	92	128	84	98.6	130	86	100.6	132	80	94	128	82	97.3	136	86	97.3	136	80	96.6	128	76	93.3	0	0	0	0	
84	99.3	132	74	109	130	70	90	106	76	90	126	80	97.3	136	84	101.3	134	80	98	138	86	103	110	70	83.3	0	0	0	0	
76	93.3	128	86	101	130	90	103	120	80	93.3	122	78	94	128	76	93.3	116	74	88	120	84	96	126	76	95.3	0	0	0	0	
58	70	120	70	100	124	72	89.3	120	68	80	118	72	88.6	126	74	91.3	120	78	92	120	80	93.3	118	78	90.6	0	0	0	0	
70	82	136	80	103	130	84	99	104	86	87.3	94	72	87	114	76	88	112	72	85	120	86	97.3	132	84	100	0	0	0	0	
60	72	110	70	107	100	66	77.3	122	80	97.3	118	68	76.6	96	62	73.3	120	80	93.3	118	78	91.3	134	88	103	0	0	0	0	
74	88	118	78	83.3	112	70	84	128	82	97.3	108	78	91.5	116	80	92	120	80	93.3	128	78	92.6	116	76	89.3	0	0	0	0	
70	84.6	118	78	83.3	122	76	91.3	124	78	93.3	110	70	82.6	136	90	105.3	120	82	95.6	116	76	87.3	122	82	95.3	0	0	0	0	
76	85.3	108	78	86.6	100	68	78.6	114	74	87.3	110	70	83.3	118	70	86	120	76	94	134	86	102	126	78	94	0	0	0	0	
84	90	110	80	97.3	108	84	95.3	124	74	90.6	116	76	95.3	126	76	90.6	108	74	88	136	86	102.6	132	78	96	0	0	0	0	
82	93.3	124	84	100	118	80	96.6	130	84	99.3	118	72	92.6	136	84	101.3	116	74	86.6	118	78	91.3	132	84	100	0	0	0	0	
70	82	128	84	113	124	80	94.6	120	74	89.3	180	72	87	128	76	93.3	120	82	95.6	126	80	95.3	140	80	100	0	0	0	0	
82	93.3	138	86	115	130	84	99.3	116	74	88	110	76	90	126	74	91.3	136	80	98.6	128	76	93.3	122	86	98	0	0	0	0	
70	82	114	66	84.6	118	76	90	102	74	83.3	110	76	95.3	114	76	88	126	70	88.6	118	78	91.3	118	86	90	3	0	0	0	
64	80.6	98	62	100	126	76	92.3	120	76	90	122	70	83.3	96	62	73.3	126	78	94	126	80	95.3	122	88	99.3	0	0	0	0	
84	90	118	78	83.3	118	80	96.6	120	80	93.3	132	80	94	116	80	92	134	80	98	128	76	93.3	110	70	83.3	0	0	0	0	
60	78	118	78	83.3	124	80	94.6	132	88	102	110	80	97.3	112	74	86.6	116	74	88	128	74	92	126	76	95.3	0	0	0	0	
74	88	108	78	86.6	130	84	99.3	128	78	94	116	76	95.3	114	76	88.6	120	78	92	114	72	86	118	78	90.6	0	0	0	0	
70	84.6	110	80	97.3	118	76	90	106	86	102	118	72	92.6	114	76	88.6	112	72	85	118	76	90	132	84	100	0	0	0	0	
76	85.3	124	84	100	126	76	92.3	134	68	80	180	72	87	118	84	95.6	120	80	93.3	120	80	93.3	134	88	103	3	0	0	0	
84	90	114	66	84.6	134	80	94.6	106	76	90	110	76	90	114	74	94	120	82	95.6	120	86	97.3	132	84	100	0	0	0	0	
82	93.3	110	70	107	118	70	84.3	120	80	93.3	114	76	95.3	136	90	105.3	116	74	86.6	118	78	91.3	134	88	103	0	0	0	0	
70	82	110	80	97.3	116	74	88	120	68	80	120	70	84.6	118	70	86	120	82	95.6	120	78	92.6	116	76	89.3	0	0	0	0	
64	80.6	92	70	77.3	100	70	80	104	86	87.3	116	82	94.6	120	76	90.6	118	82	89.3	120	76	87.3	122	82	95.3	0	0	0	0	
84	90	122	82	95.3	112	70	84	122	80	97.3	118	72	92.6	136	84	101.3	128	76	92.6	130	82	98	126	78	94	0	0	0	0	
60	78	124	84	100	122	76	91.3	128	82	97.3	110	78	91.5	128	76	93.3	120	76	94	130	74	92	122	70	97.3	3	0	0	0	
76	89.3	118	78	83.3	100	68	78.6	124	78	93.3	122	70	83.3	126	74	91.3	120	78	92	130	80	96.6	116	70	85.3	0	0	0	0	
82	93.3	108	78	86.6	108	84	95.3	114	74	87.3	130	80	94	114	76	88	120	80	88.6	138	86	103	106	70	82	0	0	0	0	
74	88	110	80	97.3	118	80	96.6	132	88	102	136	80	96.6	96	62	73.3	136	86	97.3	120	84	96	118	78	90.6	0	0	0	0	
76	85.3	124	84	100	116	74	88	128	78	94	180	90	105.3	118	70	86	128	76	93.3	120	80	93.3	132	84	100	0	0	0	0	
84	95.3	128	84	113	100	66	77.3	120	74	89.3	160	76	90	120	76	90.6	108	74	95.3	120	86	97.3	134	88	103	0	0	0	0	
74	88	138	86	115	108	84	95.3	116	74	88	108	78	91.5	136	84	101.3	98	62	74	118	78	91.3	116	76	89.3	0	0	0	0	
70	84.6	116	78	96.6	100	76	84	102	74	83.3	110	70	82.6	128	76	93.3	120	78	92	120	78	92.6	122	82	95.3	3	0	0	0	
76	85.3	122	76	109	130	86	101	120	76	90	110	70	83.3	126	74	91.3	112	72	85	120	76	87.3	126	78	94	0	0	0	0	
84	90	132	82	98.6	118	80	96.6	120	80	93.3	116	76	95.3	114	76	88	120	80	93.3	108	72	86	122	70	97.3	0	0	0	0	

